

“HANDWRITING RECOGNITION USING HYBRID TECHNIQUE”

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ABSTRACT

The main Purpose of this work is to highlights the recognition of hand-written Content/character problems that have been proposed. This study shows the emerging and widely used in many vision-based applications in recent years. In this work, the drawback of conventional handwriting recognition utilizes the statistical characteristics of individual Content/characters, and different subsets to recognize the different Content/characters are overcome. This presented work demonstrates a mixture of the MLPNN/HMM model for operational Hindi writing recognition. The planned structure is proposed on behalf of HMMs and various-Layer Perceptron Neural Linkages. Signal of input is generated toward uninterrupted knocks named segments constructed proceeding of the Elliptical approach through scrutinizing the extremisms arguments of the rounded rapidity outline. The linkage of neural accomplished through subdivision near relative evidence stays castoff near-abstract course atmosphere prospects. Proposed outcomes of that system remain translated through HMMs towards run after attractiveness of equal credit. Now appraisals are scheduled to DBMs Hindi database which proficient 97.8% attractiveness appreciation exactness that signifies statistically significantly imperative trendy evaluation through attractiveness appreciation exactitudes attained after advanced online Hindi systems. Methodology used is to mitigate this problem several works have been motivated to incorporate a deep learning model for handwriting recognition and achieved significant performance improvement in recent times. In deep learning models, Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are providing promising solutions to automate the distinct feature extraction from all given training samples. In this work pre-processing measures have been used to explore the boundary details of input samples for CNN-based handwritten character and digit recognition systems. Here, we proposed a hybrid novel CNN model which combines the detailed feature extraction for final classification. The proposed CNN framework is trained using the Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology (MNIST) database.

The main finding in term of performance validation includes both character and digits classification from given benchmark image sets. The validation also includes some self-build handwritten characters and digits for analyzing its resistance to the real-time capture. From the experimental results, it is observed that the variation inaccuracies are significant with the number of layers used in the CNN network. Finally, to validate the performance metrics of the proposed handwritten character recognition system it is compared

with the existing state-of-the-art HCR models in terms of overall recognition accuracy. Based on the proposed model that system remains translated through HMMs towards run after attractiveness of equal credit. Now appraisals are scheduled to DBMs Hindi database which proficient 97.8% attractiveness appreciation exactness that signifies statistically significantly imperative trendy evaluation through attractiveness appreciation exactitudes attained after advanced online Hindi systems. In this work, the drawback of conventional handwriting recognition utilizes the statistical characteristics of individual Content/characters, and different subsets to recognize the different Content/characters are overcome. The objectives for accommodating handwritten content/characters written in different formats are difficult to accomplish irrespective of the methodologies used for classification. A new conceptual of mixture of the MLPNN/HMM model has been proposed for operations of Hindi writing recognition techniques based on Perceptron Neural Linkages.

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ABBREVIATIONS

CNN	Convolutions Neural Network
SIFT	Scale Invariant Feature Transform
MNIST	Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology database
AI	Artificial Intelligence
HCR	Handwritten Content/characters
SVM	Support Vector Machine
(NFS)	Neuro-Fuzzy Systems
GA	Genetic algorithm
HMM	Hidden Markov Model
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
FPGA	<i>Field Programmable Gate Arrays</i>
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OCR	Optical character recognition
DCNNs	Developed Deep convolutional neural networks
MLPANN	Multi-Layer Perceptron Artificial Neural Network

Chapter-1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Authentication is one of the important factors in order to grant access to a facility or service to certain people. The authentication is important in the sense that only few people are allowed to access the facility or service and all other should be prevented from getting the access. To grant the authentication for access verification is important. Verification can be either manual or automatic. Manual verification includes documents verification or confirmation by any other individual like comparing the photographs or signatures. Automatic verification includes processing the information by an automatic system or AI (Artificial Intelligence) system. Examples of automatic verification include passwords, electronic access with ID cards or PIN (Personal Identification Number). Data that is collected from a person is processed by an electronic system. However, these access credentials can be forgotten by a person or can be stolen by others. Hence it is imperative to make the system fail proof so that only authorized personal are allowed the access to a facility, service or application. Biometrics is one such kind of data that is specific to a person, but cannot be stolen or forged by others that easily.

The word biometrics is a Greek word meaning life (bio) and measurement (metric). The measurement of life means measuring the physical characteristic from a subject that has life. Examples of biometric include collecting the finger prints, iris, blood sample or hair for DNA, geometries of hand or fingers etc. These factors are associated with some shape or characteristic of the person's body. These types of biometrics that can be collected from the human body can be termed as physiological biometrics. There are also other types of biometrics that are behavioral in nature. That means, the behavior of each person can be characterized separately and that information can be used to identify the person. These biometrics are not part of the person's body, it belongs to human behavior. Examples of behavioral biometrics include signature, handwritten text, key strokes, voice etc as shown in Fig 1.1. The physiological and behavioral biometrics has its own advantages and limitations. For example, the physiological biometrics cannot be modified by a person though it belongs to him, whereas the behavioral biometrics can be modified by force or practice by a person. Also the behavioral biometrics change with time and hence it is dynamic in nature.

Traditional systems use the information that you have and biometric systems use the information that you are.

Figure 1.1: Various Categories of Biometrics

A typical biometric consists of four modules, namely,

- Database of users
- Image acquisition
- Pattern analysis or feature extraction
- Recognition module

Database of users have all the images or data captured from the users. This database is based on historical data and this data is used to train and build a model to recognize new or future inputs. Database of users will have only one type of data for each user and every data record has a label associated with it. The label usually acts as identity of the person like name, identification number or index. If face recognition is to be performed, then this database will have all the facial images with proper labels. Similarly, if the person identification is based on finger prints, then this database is comprised of only finger prints of all the persons. Any new image input to the model, it will identify the closest match with the

train or reference database and extract the label information from it. The extracted information is attached to new input image.

Image acquisition is required to create the new images. For example, if it is required to identify a person who is entering into an airport, then the high-resolution cameras can capture image of the person and send it to face recognition module to identify the person. In case of signature recognition, then scanner of the image is the image acquisition system. The scanned signature is input to the model to identify the person with the signature. Feature extraction module consists of machine learning algorithms to extract the features from the train data as well as test data. Features are the patterns that lie in the input data. Machine learning algorithms used for feature extraction can be statistical or non-statistical algorithms or computer vision algorithms.

Recognition module is the model that has been trained using the data from database. Once the model has been trained, parameters of the model are stored and it can be used to classify any new images that are captured as part of the image acquisition system. There are different varieties of recognition modules. In the first type, models learn from database and the images in database are not required after the model is built. In second type, model will extract the features and compare it with the features extracted from the database images. The matching image is determined and person is identified. Identification of pattern means, comparing the input image with all the images in database and identifying the matching image in the data base, whereas verification of pattern means, comparing the input pattern with the pattern extracted from the image of that person which is stored in the database. If the patterns match, then that person is verified and authenticated. In a biometric system, enrollment and authentication are two important parts. In enrollment, the biometric details of a person are added to the database. In authentication, the person in query is verified.

1.2 Handwriting Frame Work

Hand writing recognition also includes writer identification. For the purpose of writer recognition, many samples of written text are collected. Few samples of text by a writer are shown in Figure 1.2. A writer identification system will be trained for these samples of text along with the writer information. Various components of writer identification system are shown in Fig 3. The hand written documents are subjected to machine learning algorithm to understand the pattern. The documents are in the form of digital text which is extracted from

the scanned pages using optical character recognition. Features that are extracted from the text are words present in the text. These features are input to the classifiers which will identify the writer. If there are multiple writers in the database of training set, then each writer is assigned score. The writer with highest score is the most probable writer for that text. Finally, the writer with highest score is selected as the writer.

Figure 1.2: Writer Identification Framework

Accuracy of the writer identification system depends on the two parts in the framework shown in Fig 2. The two parts are features of hand writing and classifier. The features can be extracted from the text samples collected from different writers using supervised and unsupervised learning techniques. Again, as discussed before, the features can be static features or dynamic features. The static features are those that are part of the written text. Dynamic features are those that are to be captured at the time of writing the text. This is possible only in the online recording of the text. Figure 1.3 shows the static and dynamic features of the text. All features related to document, paragraphs, line, sentence, word or characters are known as static features. Features related to speed of movement of the pen, pressure applied, number of pauses etc can be treated as dynamic features.

Figure 1.3: Static and Dynamic Features of Text Writing

1.3 Scope of Further Research

1) Purpose: This presented work demonstrates a mixture of the MLPNN/HMM model for operational Hindi writing recognition. The planned structure is proposed on behalf of HMMs and various-Layer Perceptions Neural Linkages. Signal of input is generated toward uninterrupted knocks named segments constructed proceeding of the Elliptical approach through scrutinizing the extremisms arguments of the rounded rapidity outline. The linkage of neural accomplished through subdivision near relative evidence stays castoff near-abstract course atmosphere prospects. Proposed outcomes of that system remain translated through HMMs towards run after attractiveness of equal credit. Now appraisals are scheduled to DBMs Hindi database which proficient 97.8% attractiveness appreciation exactness that signifies statistically significantly imperative trendy evaluation through attractiveness appreciation exactitudes attained after advanced online Hindi systems.

2) Purpose: In this work highlights the recognition of hand-written Content/character problems that have been proposed. This study shows the emerging and widely used in many vision-based applications in recent years. In this work, the drawback of conventional

handwriting recognition utilizes the statistical characteristics of individual Content/characters, and different subsets to recognize the different Content/characters are overcome.

1.4 Modeling of Hybrid CNN Framework

In recent years automatic handwriting character recognition has been emerging steadily due to its wide range of enormous application potentials such as banking sectors, mobile phones, and computer-aided education [1]. As compared to other recognition systems HCR is dealing with several complications due to the enormous variety of handwriting styles of everyone. As compared to printed Content/characters recognizing handwritten Content/characters are comes with several challenges as follows: (1) Handwritten Content/characters comes with morphological and scale variations within the same classes; (2) Inter class similarity level of some of similar Content/characters are very high which makes poor detection rate. It is categorized into two types such as online and Offline HCR [2]. In both, cases for improved recognition accuracy different segmentation and feature extraction methods are used in many existing works. The recent advancements in character recognition technology emerging several parametric constraints that can extend its usage in a wide range of applications that required unique character identification [3][4]. In general character recognition are deployed with detailed analyzes of each unit to formulate the feature sets and extended with large sets of multi-modal data attributes to improve the accuracy[5]. Morphological measurements are the widely preferred technique to explore the dimension of any object of interest. Most of the existing HCR methods formulate templates with finite shape features and showed potential misclassification issues over features set level optimization [6].

In some cases, thinning of the input image is performed as pre-processing blocks just before the ROI segmentation [7]. During boundary evaluation, the lines that are separating each letter that is available in the document are explored as an extension to the pre-processing phase. This can be accomplished in many ways such as linear object projections or binary thresholding or clustering of the objects. This Character Segmentation segments each content/character forward to these objects into the feature extraction phase [8]. Finally, HCR allows some contextual information from each object to carry out auto-classification. The aim of this work is to develop a hybrid model of a powerful Convolution Neural Networks (CNN) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) for recognition of handwritten digit from MNIST

dataset. The proposed hybrid model combines the key properties of both the classifiers. In the proposed hybrid model, CNN works as an automatic feature extractor and SVM works as a binary classifier. The MNIST dataset of handwritten digits is used for training and testing the algorithm adopted in the proposed model. The MNIST dataset consists of handwritten digits images which are diverse and highly distorted. The receptive field of CNN helps in automatically extracting the most distinguishable features from these handwritten digits. patterns and handwriting styles of individuals adds to the complexity of the recognition system. In the area of handwriting recognition, several methods have been proposed in the literature such as Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Neuro-Fuzzy Systems (NFS), Support Vector Machine (SVM) and deep learning-based classifiers [1-9]. Although decent recognition accuracy has been reported by these classifiers; handwriting digit recognition is still an open research problem and demands for exploring new techniques and methodologies that would further improve the performance in terms of recognition accuracy, running time and computational complexity. Therefore, in this work, a framework of hybrid CNN-SVM is proposed for handwritten digit recognition. The focus of the work is to extract the features from the input handwritten digit images of MNIST dataset using CNN. These learned features are then passed to the SVM classifier for the proposed handwritten digits recognition experiment. A lot of research work based on extracting handcrafted features has been reported in the literature. This manually feature extraction method is a tedious process and needs human expertise. Also, the handcrafted feature extraction method involves a trade-off between efficiency and recognition accuracy because the processing of extraneous features may increase computation overhead leading to the poor performance of the recognition system. On the other hand, non-handcrafted features extraction process comprises of retrieving features directly from the raw images. This method eliminates the necessity of collecting prior knowledge and design details of features.

The major advantage of using the CNN model is that it exploits the topological information present in the input and is invariant to basic transformations like rotation, translation etc. On the other hand, MLP models never considers detailed topology information of input and are not suitable for complex problems

1.5 Mixture of MLPNN/HMM

Imitating humanoid capability trendy mainframe suggestions remain motionless stimulating notwithstanding the enormous developments that happened fashionable the park of intelligence derives in an artificial solicitation. Moreover, the script appreciation sphere through the dual twigs disconnected then operational takes placed in the concentration on behalf of previous periods. Authentic consequences remain actual encouraging plus rendering towards nonfiction of appreciation accurateness charges conveyed through countless organizations be situated above 85%. Aimed at Hindi calligraphy then owing toward the situation lettering physiognomies that container remains enlightened trendy supplementary minutiae cutting-edge [1], unevenness, touching typescripts, attendance of strings, accents custom, moreover state-owned for less in terms of development besides that requested by way of resolved badly-behaved.

Numerous methodologies have been industrialized then Concealed HMMs models which are the best innovative tools are using this generation [2-5]. Moreover, remain numerical representations that adopt tremendously well-organized trendy the arena for involuntary language gratitude. For achievement takes interested fresh efforts toward contrivance HMMs trendy atmosphere gratitude for connected before disconnected. Thus, custom trendy script appreciation ampule remain clarified through the competence toward section then identify unwritten calligraphy that's build up selfsame multifaceted after consuming obvious approaches. Numerous connections related to neural constructions consume stayed rummage-sale similarly [6-8]. Therefore remained rummage-sale essentially aimed at inaccessible atmosphere appreciation. However, it's mainly owing to previously originated numbers desirable on behalf of teaching [9]. Therefore, a mixture technique uniting the dual kinds of the overhead statistics appears towards remaining gifted toward profits recompenses for various outsized as well as setting demonstrating through the connectivity of neural though benefitting since for Monrovia arrangement exhibiting [10-22]. The aforementioned efforts happen popular for nonfiction besides were selfsame effective on behalf of together operational and disconnected script appreciation [11-26]. Therefore, connectivity in terms of neural is being used for getting the results comment prospects used for HMMs. For the emerging field of sectors, development is working towards feature in dissimilar periods for the organization then towards deliberate various encounters for every period. Lastly it determination shot for challenging outcomes grounded proceeding for script data [14-15].

1.6 Problem Statement

Writer recognition is a growing field of interest in the research community. Based on the literature review conducted, it is observed that there are many methods developed to improve the performance of the writer identification and verification systems. Methods like Weighted Euclidean Distance, Linear Discriminant Classifier, k-Nearest Neighbors, and Hidden Markov Models have been in focus in this area of research. There is also a great deal of attempts made in the application of Convolutional Neural Networks in writer identification.

Of all the methods surveyed thus far, HMM seems to be the fastest method to deal with large datasets for a given hardware configuration. The advantage comes from representing the states of the model through representative feature vectors. Instead of using the pixel intensities directly in the model like it is done in many other methods, it is subjected to dimensionality reduction with various transformation methods like KLT, DCT or SVD.

Deep learning is the fastest growing field of research in the recent past. No research area has gained so much interest and attention in recent years like deep learning in the past few years. Almost every day there is a progress in computational methods and development of libraries for various applications. Numerous developments have been reported in MATLAB, Python, PyTorch, Tensor flow etc. Advantages of deep learning lies in its versatility ease of use of libraries, flexibility to choose various techniques, standardization of code etc.

Another important component in implementation of writer identification is integrating the methods like HMM and Deep learning so that benefits of both the methods can be availed. The benefits of HMM are feature extraction, that of deep learning are extracting non-linear relations. No significant progress is achieved in using hybrid methods. But in general, hybrid methods were used with two methods that belong to same category like traditional statistical methods or deep learning methods. There is not much research witnessed in integration of methods from different approaches.

In this research work, an attempt is made to integrate the traditional statistical methods, deep learning methods. Purpose of this integration is to achieve speed, accuracy and ease of usage. Objectives of this research are set to achieve the goals of improved accuracy and speed of execution. Objectives are listed below.

1.7 Research Objectives:

The main research focused on “**HANDWRITING RECOGNITION USING HYBRID TECHNIQUE**”

1. To implement and measure the performance of HMM (Hidden Markov Model) for writer identification on User database and IAM dataset.
2. To implement and measure the performance of MLP (Multi-Layer Perceptron models) and HMM (Hidden Markov Models) for writer identification on User database and IAM dataset.
3. To implement and measure the performance of CNN (convolutional neural network) and HMM (Hidden Markov Models) for writer identification on User database and IAM dataset.
4. To implement and measure the performance of HMM (Hidden Markov Models) and MLP (Multi-Layer Perceptron models) for writer identification on User database and IAM dataset.
5. To implement and measure the performance of HMM (Hidden Markov Models) and CNN (convolutional neural network) for writer identification on User database and IAM dataset
6. To develop HMM Model with other feature vectors like DCT, KLT or PCA coefficients for writer identification dataset.
7. Extend HMMCNN model to other languages.
8. Extend Model to dynamic characteristics.
9. Improve HMMCNN model with Google inception models.
10. Measure the performance of HMMCNN on cloud environments like AWS or Microsoft Azure or GCP and compare with FPGA.

Above objectives are set, based on the gaps identified in the literature, to achieve better accuracies and speed of execution than the current methods.

1.8 Thesis Organizations:

Proposed “**HANDWRITING RECOGNITION USING HYBRID TECHNIQUE**” into six chapters.

Chapter –1: Discuss the introduction and motivation, research objectives, problem statement and Scope of further studies in the field of face detection.

Chapter -2: The presents a detailed literature survey on “Modeling of Hybrid CNN Framework for Handwritten Character” and “Digit Recognition System and A Mixture of MLPNN/HMM Demonstrates the Procedure for Online Hindi Writing Recognition”.

Chapter - 3: Discussed the Modeling of Hybrid CNN Framework for Handwritten Character.

Chapter - 4: Digit Recognition System and A Mixture of MLPNN/HMM Demonstrates the Procedure for Online Hindi Writing Recognition.

Chapter - 5: Results and Discussions.

Chapter- 6: Conclusion and future scope.

Chapter-2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

We have reviewed several research papers of different journals and conferences published on this research area. Research has been categorized “**HANDWRITING RECOGNITION USING HYBRID TECHNIQUE.**” Methods are highly sensitive to error accumulation over input. For handwritten documents, significant performance gaps are notable despite the advancement over time. But still, the importance of HCR systems is essential for processing any language even though its results are far from perfect. In some cases, complete probabilistic methods are used for HCR for monolithic scan document systems and used as a prominent computational kernel in the NLP process. To narrow down the penalty gap using the most appropriate feature set models and use the most useful templates for network training is investigated in many recent works.

Much research has been devoted to natural language processing (NLP) to process over English languages rather than native languages. However, to perform data assessment over HCR performance and various stages of the recognition process different versions of the same input document is need to be produced which can incorporate all nonlinear changes. In [6] analysed the impact of the nonlinear changes that may occur over input over natural language processing (NLP) performance. Hereby performing various assessments such as ROI segmentation, letter recognition, data retrieval, feature set modelling, etc. over existing OCR models and its impact in NLP is discussed. In [7] developed Tamil character recognition using novel OCR and NLP techniques. For performance validation, several inscription documents are collected from the Tamil Nadu government Archaeological Department and carried out pre-processing and ROI segmentation process. For ROI segmentation input RGB color images are transformed into greyscale and linearization is performed based on a threshold value. For template generation highly unified Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) is used to explore the finite discrimination of each character. Content/characters are identified based on only the quantifiable textual features extracted leads to poor accuracy in the case of illuminated images. Extracted values with values outside these ROI ranges must be discarded from the classification. In [8] investigate various state-of-the-art NLP models with various levels and types of OCR noise to prove the sensitive level of classification performance. The performance degradation of each model is systematically analysed using different languages. And also showed that many dictionary-

based extrinsic OCR evaluations lead complexity and variability of the anatomic shapes will be varying depending on character types. In [9] fast Boolean matching and binary external symmetry axis constellation are jointly used to explore the finite details of each character pattern. Here orientations are encoded and combined to generate feature subset and hierarchical classification is introduced and recognized different Content/characters based on its discrimination in hamming distance over-extracted feature.

In [10] investigates the potential benefits of the MNIST dataset invalidating various CNN and deep learning approaches invented for handwritten character recognition systems. Significant challenges faced by different artificial intelligence techniques are discussed and relevant performance metrics are also analysed in detail. In [11] developed multi-class Support Vector Machine model for an off-line HCR system which includes multi-modal feature extraction techniques. Here Feature set includes spatial information about individual Content/characters, mean, standard deviation, and gradient information. HCR system introduced in [12] using improved neural network technology mitigates the issues related to complex handwritten character recognition. For an improved classification rate, the input image is pre-processed and extracted structural features with associated optimization for multiple neural networks. The compatibility issues of existing CNN are discussed in [13] which provide the inherent statistical characteristics like computation cost, huge memory space, and requirement of larger sets of training samples. This property makes most of the conventional CNN not applicable for resource and energy-constrained IoT and mobile devices. To mitigate this problem Global Weighted Average Pooling model is introduced to optimize the parameters involved in a fully connected layer without compromising the quality metrics. Finally, the overall inference time of CNN is optimally reduced using the cascaded model. In [14] developed deep convolutional neural networks (DCNNs) and analysed its performance metrics in Handwritten Bangla character recognition. DCNN offered discriminative features extraction and improved invariance over nonlinear distortions in the input during validation.

Deep learning model developed in [15] for character recognition with improved recognition rate using different types of directional feature maps in CNN network. This system also includes a novel data augmentation model formulated based on statistical characteristics of handwritten Chinese content/characters. For better recognition rate enlarged sets are used for training that incorporates global transformation associated with relevant local distortion. In [16] optimize the computation cost of CNN using some appropriate

compression based on a unified algorithm with some insignificant accuracy loss. The CNN network structure is simplified using channel pruning strategy and network parameters are optimized using quantization technique. In [17] proposed a novel multi-objective Jaya CNN feature learning model to learn all potential features from input images directly. Here an optimizer and multiplication layer is introduced with an activation layer. The network model learns the spatial patterns by analysing the spatial correlations and the Multiplication layer is used to formulate the learning model. The weights used at each layer are normalized using an optimizer. Finally, it has experimented in the OCR system and performance metrics are validated using inter-class similarity and intra-class variance associated during recognition of Content/characters. In [18] developed optimal feature subset generation for recognizing the handwritten Tamil Content/characters using the nearest interest point classifier model. Here most simplified matching vector-based approach is used for classification with an accuracy of 90.2% by incorporating a detailed feature analysis process after the feature extraction process.

In [17] portrays a novel methodology for signature verification and identification proof in an offline situation dependent on a quasi-multi resolution technique using GSC (Gradient, Structural, and Concavity) features for feature extraction. These highlights when utilized at the word level, rather than the character level, yield promising outcomes with correctness as high as 78% and 93% for check and ID, separately. This strategy was effectively utilized in our past theory of individuality of handwriting created at CEDAR-dependent on getting inside and between author statistical distance distributions. In [17], investigating mark check and ID as offline handwriting verification and identification process separately, we delineate a mapping from the handwriting domain to the signature domain.

Chaudhuri et al. (1998) have completely printed the Bangla OCR system [1]. Bazzi et al. (1999) have an Omni font open-vocabulary OCR system for English and Arabic [2]. Mahmud et al. (2003) have a complete OCR system for continuous Bengali characters [3]. Lehal et al. (2009) have a complete machine-printed Gurmukhi OCR system [4]. Kolak et al. (2003) has a generative probabilistic OCR model for NLP applications [5]. Van et al. (2020). Have assessing the impact of OCR quality on downstream NLP tasks [6]. Manigandan et al. (2017, August). Tamil character recognition from ancient epigraphical inscription using OCR [7]. Hamdi et al. (2020, August) have assessed and minimized the impact of OCR quality on named entity recognition [8]. Dash et al. (2016) developed BESAC explored Binary External Symmetry Axis Constellation for unconstrained handwritten character recognition [9].

Baldominos et al. (2019) have surveyed handwritten character recognition with most and emnist[10]. Katiyar et al. (2017) has an offline handwritten character recognition system using a support vector machine. American Journal of Neural Networks and Applications[11]. Li et al. (2017) have handwritten character recognition technology combined with artificial intelligence [12]. Li, Z et al. (2018) have built efficient CNN architecture for offline handwritten Chinese character recognition [13]. Alom et al. (2018) worked on handwritten Bangla character recognition using state-of-the-art deep convolutional neural networks. Computational intelligence and neuroscience [14]. Qu et al. (2018) worked on data augmentation and directional feature maps extraction for in-air handwritten Chinese character recognition based on the convolutional neural network [15]. Gan et al. (2020) have compressed the CNN architecture for in-air handwritten Chinese character recognition[16]. Das et al. (2020) have published MJCN: Multi-objective Jaya Convolutional Network for handwritten optical character recognition [17]. Deepa et al. (2020) have presented a novel nearest interest point classifier for offline Tamil handwritten character recognition [18]. Ghadekar et al. (2018) have worked on handwritten digit and letter recognition using hybrid DWT-DCT with known and SVM classifiers [19]. Cavalin et al. (2018) have Confusion matrix-based building of hierarchical classification [20].

2.1 Related Research on Modeling of Hybrid CNN Framework for Handwritten Character and Digit Recognition System

Chaudhuri et al. (1998) completed Optical Character Recognition (OCR) system for printed Bangla, the fourth most popular script in the world, is presented. This is the first OCR system among all script forms used in the Indian sub-continent. The problem is difficult because (i) there are about 300 basics, modified and compound character shapes in the script, (ii) the characters in a word are topologically connected and (iii) Bangla is an inflectional language. In our system the document image captured by Flat-bed scanner is subject to skew correction, text graphics separation, line segmentation, zone detection, word and character segmentation using some conventional and some newly developed techniques. From zonal information and shape characteristics, the basic, modified and compound characters are separated for the convenience of classification. The basic and modified characters which are about 75 in number and which occupy about 96% of the text corpus are recognized by a structural-feature-based tree classifier. The compound characters are recognized by a tree classifier followed by template-matching approach. The feature detection is simple and robust where preprocessing like thinning and pruning are avoided. The character unigram statistics

is used to make the tree classifier efficient. Several heuristics are also used to speed up the template matching approach. A dictionary-based error-correction scheme has been used where separate dictionaries are compiled for root word and suffixes that contain morpho-syntactic informations as well. For single font clear documents 95.50%-wordlevel (which is equivalent to 99.10%-character level) recognition accuracy has been obtained. Extension of the work to Devnagari, the third most popular script in the world, is also discussed.

2.2 Noteworthy Contribution in this field:

J. Mahmud et al. (2003) concerned with a complete optical character recognition (OCR) system for Bengali character. Recognition is done for both isolated and continuous printed multi font Bengali characters. Preprocessing steps includes segmentation in various levels, noise removal and scaling. Freeman chain code has been calculated from scaled character which is further processed to obtain a discriminating set of feature vectors for the recognizer. The unknown samples are classified using feed forward neural network-based recognition scheme. It has been found from experimental results that success rate is approximately 98% for isolated characters and 96% for continuous characteristics.

Manigandan et al. (2017) Recognition of ancient Tamil characters is one of the challenging tasks for Epigraphers as the language has evolved with different characters set. If the inscriptions are on stone walls, it adds even more complexity in identifying characters. This proposed work mainly focuses on recognition of various Tamil characters between 9th and 12th centuries using OCR and NLP techniques. In this work, the inscription images collected from Tamil Nadu, Archaeological Department are pre-processed and segmented. During the segmentation process the color images were converted to gray image and to binary image based on threshold value. From segmented, image features like number of lines, curves, loops and dots have been extracted using Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) algorithms for each letter to identify the exact character. Characters will be classified and constructed based on Vectors extracted, using Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier and the patterns of the character will be matched with known characters and predicted using Trigram technique. Each identified character will be assigned with its corresponding Unicode value and it will be updated in the image corpus for further character identification, and to make the system in identifying the characters more effectively. Thus, the proposed system can solve the major problems in reading the inscription images.

Ahmed Hamdiet al. (2020) In digital libraries, the accessibility of digitized documents is directly related to the way they are indexed. Named entities are one of the main entry points used to search and retrieve digital documents. However, most digitized documents are indexed through their OCR version and OCR errors may hinder their accessibility. This paper aims to quantitatively estimate the impact of OCR quality on the performance of named entity recognition (NER). We tested state-of-the-art NER techniques over several evaluation benchmarks, and experimented with various levels and types of synthesized OCR noise so as to estimate the impact of OCR noise on NER performance. We share all corresponding datasets. To the best of our knowledge, no other research work has systematically studied the impact of OCR on named entity recognition over datasets in multiple languages. The final outcome of this study is an evaluation over historical newspaper data of the national library of Finland, resulting in an increase of around 11% points in terms of F1-measure over the best-known results to this day.

We propose a novel perception driven feature extraction called binary external symmetry axis constellation (BESAC) and a fast Boolean matching character recognition technique. A constellation model using a set of external symmetry axes which are perceptually significant can uniquely represent a handwritten character pattern. This model generates two histograms of orientations that are binary coded and concatenated to produce the proposed BESAC feature. A two-stage classification strategy is adopted where a parallel Hamming Distance dissimilarity matching is performed on the extracted BESAC feature to achieve fast recognition along with perceptual closure part detection on look-alike characters. We adopt a 10-fold cross validation strategy to evaluate the performance of our algorithm on two major Indian languages, Bangla and Odia with four benchmark databases (ISI Kolkata Bangla numeral, ISI Kolkata Odia and IITBBS Odia numeral, and a newly created IITBBS Odia character database). The average time for classifying an unknown handwritten character is reported to be significantly less than the existing methods. The average recognition accuracy using the proposed approach is proved to outperform the state-of-the-art accuracy results on ISI Kolkata Odia numeral database (99.35%), IITBBS Odia numeral (98.9%), ISI Kolkata Bangla numeral database (99.48%) and IITBBS Odia character (95.01%) database.

Shuai Li. et al. (2017) The offline handwritten character recognition is an important branch of character recognition, which involves character recognition, image processing, digital signal processing, artificial intelligence, fuzzy mathematics, information theory, computer and other disciplines. In the process of off-line handwritten character recognition, it

only processed two-dimensional character dot images, and there are problems such as too many character classes, complex font structure, large deformation of handwritten characters and other issues. Currently off-line handwritten character recognition technology is still immature, which is still in the laboratory research stage. This paper attempted to combine neural network technology and character recognition technology, and came up with effectively new method of handwritten character recognition, finding a feasible new way to solve practical difficulties between handwritten character recognition. In this paper, according to the building process of the multi-level recognition system, the article introduced the preprocessing of character image, character feature extraction, neural networks and optimization algorithms as well as multiple neural networks in turn. In the end, based on experimental results by identification system in MATLAB, the author comparatively discussed the performance of the recognition system, analyzing the notices of establishing the identification system.

Zhiyuan Li et al. (2018) Deep convolution networks based methods have brought great breakthrough in images classification, which provides an end-to-end solution for handwritten Chinese character recognition (HCCR) problem through learning discriminative features automatically. Nevertheless, state-of-the-art CNNs appear to incur huge computation cost, and require the storage of a large number of parameters especially in fully connected layers, which is difficult to deploy such networks into alternative hardware device with the limit of computation amount. To solve the storage problem, we propose a novel technique called Global Weighted Average Pooling for reducing the parameters in fully connected layer without loss in accuracy. Besides, we implement a cascaded model in single CNN by adding mid output layer to complete recognition as early as possible, which reduces average inference time significantly. Experiments were performed on the ICDAR-2013 offline HCCR dataset, and it is found that the proposed approach only needs 6.9ms for classfying a chracter image on average, and achieves the state-of-the-art accuracy of 97.1% while requiring only 3.3MB for storage.

Md Zahangir Alomet al. (2018) In spite of advances in object recognition technology, handwritten Bangla character recognition (HBCR) remains largely unsolved due to the presence of many ambiguous handwritten characters and excessively cursive Bangla handwritings. Even many advanced existing methods do not lead to satisfactory performance in practice that related to HBCR. In this paper, a set of the state-of-the-art deep convolutional neural networks (DCNNs) is discussed and their performance on the application of HBCR is

systematically evaluated. The main advantage of DCNN approaches is that they can extract discriminative features from raw data and represent them with a high degree of invariance to object distortions. The experimental results show the superior performance of DCNN models compared with the other popular object recognition approaches, which implies DCNN can be a good candidate for building an automatic HBCR system for practical applications.

Dibyasundar Das et al. (2020) In recent years, the non-handcrafted feature extraction methods have gained increasing popularity for solving pattern classification tasks due to their inherent ability to extract robust features and handle outliers. However, the design of such features demands a large set of training data. Meta-heuristic optimization schemes can facilitate feature learning even with a small amount of training data. This paper presents a new feature learning mechanism called multi-objective Jaya convolutional network (MJCN) that attempts to learn meaningful features directly from the images. The proposed scheme, unlike the convolutional neural networks, comprises a convolution layer, a multiplication layer, an activation layer and an optimizer known as multi-objective Jaya optimizer (MJO). The convolution layer searches meaningful patterns in an image through the local neighborhood connections and the multiplication layer projects the convolutional response to a more compact feature space. The weights used in these layers are initialized randomly and MJO is then introduced to optimize the weights. The main objective of MJO is to maximize the inter-class distance and minimize the intra-class variance. The feature vectors are finally derived using the optimized weights. The derived features are finally fed to a set of standard classifiers for recognition of characters. The performance of the proposed model is evaluated on various benchmark datasets, namely, NITR Odia handwritten character, ISI Kolkata Odia numeral, ISI Kolkata Bangla numeral, and MNIST as well as a newly developed dataset NITR Bangla numeral. The experimental results show that the proposed scheme outperforms other state-of-the-art approaches in terms of recognition accuracy.

2.3 Problem Identification and Formulation:

In previous research has been found and arranged for a further research study for face recognition applications systems. This research work also key pointed the problems and challenges in existing works. These are as follows:

- (1) The normal GA are not applicable for the problems of face recognition or pattern recognition systems. An image file consists of a large number of evidence and individualities.

- (2) In existing system predictable to covenant by delinquent resolving in a manner with various ways of conservative computing was not highlighted.
- (3) Dissimilarity has been made between data and the pattern to accentuate the necessity for proposing the pattern systems that report pattern recognition tasks.
- (4) The Face recognition system consists of an identical massive Heap-space that includes time-intense tasks therefore GA based methodology was being used to identify the unaccusable copy inside a specific period.
- (5) Designing of fast and accurate system for face detection were challenges using existing methods.
- (6) The real challenge in neural network-based approaches is training and representing images not containing faces.
- (7) Recognizing human faces under different conditions like 5year old boy, grandma's wedding photo, face occluded, and a person with a beard are trivial but not impossible.
- (8) As the classifier complexity increases, a large amount of training examples is required.
- (9) The correctness of the classifier depends on the number of features selected while training the classifier.
A CPU real-time and accurate unconstrained face detector is still need be in investigation and design implements.

2.4 Research Agenda

2.4.1 Objectives

In previous research has been found and arranged for a further research study for handwriting recognition using hybrid technique.

1. To implement and measure the performance of HMM (Hidden Markov Model) for writer identification on User database and IAM dataset.
2. To implement and measure the performance of MLP (Multi-Layer Perception models) and HMM (Hidden Markov Models) for writer identification on User database and IAM dataset.

3. To implement and measure the performance of CNN (convolutional neural network) and HMM (Hidden Markov Models) for writer identification on User database and IAM dataset.
4. To implement and measure the performance of HMM (Hidden Markov Models) and MLP (Multi-Layer Perceptron models) for writer identification on User database and IAM dataset.
5. To implement and measure the performance of HMM (Hidden Markov Models) and CNN (convolutional neural network)
6. To develop HMM Model with other feature vectors like DCT, KLT or PCA coefficients for writer identification dataset.
7. Extend HMMCNN model to other languages.
8. Extend Model to dynamic characteristics.
9. Improve HMMCNN model with Google inception models.
10. Measure the performance of HMMCNN on cloud environments like AWS or Microsoft Azure or GCP and compare with FPGA.

Above objectives are set, based on the gaps identified in the literature, to achieve better accuracies and speed of execution than the current methods

2.5 Summary

- Reviewed several research papers of different journals and conferences published on this research area.
- Research has been categorized for handwriting recognition using hybrid technique.
- In previous research has been found and arranged for a further research study related research on modelling of hybrid CNN framework for handwritten character and digit recognition system. This research work also key pointed the problems and challenges in existing works.
- Problem identification and formulation and research agenda has clearly discussed in details.

Chapter-3

MODELING OF HYBRID CNN FRAMEWORK FOR HANDWRITTEN CHARACTER AND DIGIT RECOGNITION SYSTEM

3.1 Overview:

In this chapter we have modeling of hybrid cnn framework for handwritten character and digit recognition system. The main purpose of this chapter is to highlights the recognition of hand-written Content/character problems that have been proposed. This study shows the emerging and widely used in many vision-based applications in recent years. In this work, the drawback of conventional handwriting recognition utilizes the statistical characteristics of individual Content/characters, and different subsets to recognize the different Content/characters are overcome. The design approach is to mitigate this problem several works have been motivated to incorporate a deep learning model for handwriting recognition and achieved significant performance improvement in recent times. In deep learning models, Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are providing promising solutions to automate the distinct feature extraction from all given training samples. In this work pre-processing measures have been used to explore the boundary details of input samples for CNN-based handwritten character and digit recognition systems. Here, we proposed a hybrid novel CNN model which combines the detailed feature extraction for final classification. The proposed CNN framework is trained using the Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology (MNIST) database from Kera website in deep learning tensor flow of deep learning models. The main Findings is to performance validation includes both character and digits classification from given benchmark image sets. The validation also includes some self-build handwritten characters and digits for analyzing its resistance to the real-time capture. From the experimental results, it is observed that the variation inaccuracies are significant with the number of layers used in the CNN network. Finally, to validate the performance metrics of the proposed handwritten character recognition system it is compared with the existing state-of-the-art HCR models in terms of overall recognition accuracy. The originality In this work, is the drawback of conventional handwriting recognition utilizes the statistical characteristics of individual Content/characters, and different subsets to recognize the different Content/characters are overcome. The objectives for accommodating handwritten content/characters written in different formats are difficult to accomplish irrespective of the methodologies used for classification.

3.2 Introduction of Modeling of Hybrid CNN Framework for Handwritten Character and Digit Recognition System

In recent years automatic handwriting character recognition has been emerging steadily due to its wide range of enormous application potentials such as banking sectors, mobile phones, and computer-aided education [1]. As compared to other recognition systems HCR is dealing with several complications due to the enormous variety of handwriting styles of each individual. As compared to printed Content/characters recognizing handwritten Content/characters are comes with several challenges as follows: (1) Handwritten Content/characters comes with morphological and scale variations within the same classes; (2) Inter class similarity level of some of similar Content/characters are very high which makes poor detection rate. It is categorized into two types such as online and Offline HCR [2]. In both, cases for improved recognition accuracy different segmentation and feature extraction methods are used in many existing works. The recent advancements in character recognition technology emerging several parametric constraints that can extend its usage in a wide range of applications that required unique character identification [3][4]. In general character recognition are deployed with detailed analyzes of each unit to formulate the feature sets and extended with large sets of multi-modal data attributes to improve the accuracy[5]. Morphological measurements are the widely preferred technique to explore the dimension of any object of interest. Most of the existing HCR methods formulate templates with finite shape features and showed potential misclassification issues over features set level optimization [6].

In some cases, thinning of the input image is performed as pre-processing blocks just before the ROI segmentation [7]. During boundary evaluation, the lines that are separating each letter that is available in the document are explored as an extension to the pre-processing phase. This can be accomplished in many ways such as linear object projections or binary thresholding or clustering of the objects. This Character Segmentation segments each content/character forward to these objects into the feature extraction phase [8]. Finally, HCR allows some contextual information from each object to carry out auto-classification. Machine recognition of handwritten documents is far from reaching human like accuracy. Research initiatives are still undergoing to achieve higher recognition results that can lead to successful commercialization of optical character recognition (OCR). The challenges are mainly with unconstrained handwritten characters which, unlike machine printed texts, have numerous visual variations because of individual writing styles. State-of-the-art OCR

methodologies on alphanumeric handwritings are mostly focused on Roman script [1–5], Chinese [6–8], Arabic scripts [9–10], etc. In recent years, many researchers have been showing interest in developing OCRs on several Indian languages [11–15]. A late start in this direction is mainly attributed to many technical challenges peculiar to Indian scripts as well as lack of commercial market and dataset availability [16]. Nonetheless, India, being home to a fifth of total human population has always been a potential market that demands dedicated research effort, more so when there are close to 1600 languages and 22 among them being recognized as the official languages with distinct writing scripts. Recalling the development of CNN structure used in HCCR, increasing the size of input character image and the layers of CNN model improved classification, but also need more computation. The first successful CNN model applied in HCCR only has 4 convolutional layers and 2 fully connected layers, and achieved an accuracy of 94.47% with 170 MFLOPs [13]. And the state-of-art CNN model has 12 layers, which achieve an accuracy of 97.59% with 1.2GFLOPs [30]. It takes additional 6 times multiply-accumulation operations with 3.1% accuracy increase. This inspired us to use shallow networks to recognition most easy character images with low computational cost, and the confusing character images are fed into a deeper network. The cascaded model completes most classification with shallow network, which is able to reduce the inference time on average. Furthermore, we implement the cascaded model by adding extra classifiers on the mid layers of trained deep models. The mid output layers allow to complete classification with lower computational cost, and the final output ensure that the total model has a good performance. Besides, the average on different output results can increase the accuracy of final output. We add two mid output layers: Mid-A and Mid-B. Mid-A is located after fire4, which consist a same fire module like fire5, a global weighted average pooling layer and a softmax layer for classification

This chapter is organized as follows:

Section 3.3 gives the detailed analysis of the various related works on HCR models.

Section 3.4 describes the proposed deep learning framework for a high-performance HCR system.

Section 3.5 Performance efficiency and guaranteed recognition rate of the proposed method are discussed with analysis and performance evaluation.

Section 3.6 summarizes the work.

3.3 Character Recognition

Optical character recognition or optical character reader (OCR) is the electronic or mechanical conversion of images of typed, handwritten or printed text into machine-encoded text, whether from a scanned document, a photo of a document, a scene-photo (for example the text on signs and billboards in a landscape photo) or from subtitle text superimposed on an image (for example: from a television broadcast)[1]. Widely used as a form of data entry from printed paper data records – whether passport documents, invoices, bank statements, computerized receipts, business cards, mail, printouts of static-data, or any suitable documentation – it is a common method of digitizing printed texts so that they can be electronically edited, searched, stored more compactly, displayed on-line, and used in machine processes such as cognitive computing, machine translation, (extracted) text-to-speech, key data and text mining. OCR is a field of research in pattern recognition, artificial intelligence and computer vision.

CR engines have been developed into many kinds of domain-specific OCR applications, such as receipt OCR, invoice OCR, and check OCR, legal billing document OCR.

Figure 3.1: Classification of Optical character recognition (OCR)

They can be used for:

1. Data entry for business documents, e.g., passport, invoice, bank statement and receipt
2. Automatic number plate recognition
3. In airports, for passport recognition and information extraction
4. Automatic insurance documents key information extraction [citation needed]
5. Traffic sign recognition [9]

6. Extracting business card information into a contact list
7. More quickly make textual versions of printed documents, e.g., book scanning for Project Gutenberg
8. Make electronic images of printed documents searchable, e.g. Google Books
9. Converting handwriting in real-time to control a computer (pen computing)
10. Defeating CAPTCHA anti-bot systems, though these are specifically designed to prevent OCR.
11. The purpose can also be to test the robustness of CAPTCHA anti-bot systems.
12. Assistive technology for blind and visually impaired users.
13. Writing the instructions for vehicles by identifying CAD images in a database that are appropriate to the vehicle design as it changes in real time.
14. Making scanned documents searchable by converting them to searchable PDFs.

3.3.1 Optical character recognition (OCR) – targets typewritten text, one glyph or character at a time. Optical Character Recognition (OCR) is a method of transforming handwritten/scanned images into state-encoded values. Here digital databases are created based on multi-model texture features from each segmented ROI text Content/character and used simple machine learning approaches to recognize each Content/character. In most cases, OCR offers an improved character recognition rate with some unified segmentation model and database generation.

Figure 3.2: Optical character recognition (OCR)

3.3.2 Optical Word Recognition– targets typewritten text, one word at a time (for languages that use a space as a word divider). (Usually just called "OCR".) Advances are being made to recognize characters based on the context of the word in which they appear, as with the Predictive Optical Word Recognition algorithm from Peabody, Mass.-based Scan Soft Inc. The next step for developers is document recognition, in which the

software will use knowledge of the parts of speech and grammar to recognize individual characters.

3.3.3 Intelligent character recognition (ICR) – also targets handwritten print script or cursive text one graph or character at a time, usually involving machine learning.

Figure 3.3: Use of Intelligent Character Recognition to codify handwriting

3.3.4 Intelligent word recognition (IWR) – also targets handwritten printscript or cursive text, one word at a time. This is especially useful for languages where glyphs are not separated in cursive script.

Figure 3.4: Intelligent word recognition (IWR)

OCR is generally an "offline" process, which analyses a static document. There are cloud-based services which provide an online OCR API service. Handwriting movement analysis can be used as input to handwriting recognition.[14] Instead of merely using the shapes of glyphs and words, this technique is able to capture motions, such as the order in which segments are drawn, the direction, and the pattern of putting the pen down and

lifting it. This additional information can make the end-to-end process more accurate. This technology is also known as "on-line character recognition", "dynamic character recognition", "real-time character recognition", and "intelligent character recognition".

3.4 Handwritten Character Recognition (HCR)

Hand-written character recognition (HCR) is used to recognize the individual Content/characters using appropriate feature set modeling and machine learning algorithms. It has been widely adopted for a wide range of languages across the world and to recognize each individual written character belonging to different languages uses various image processing techniques to model the classes. As compared to other recognition methods HCR is computationally complex due to the randomness of different individual handwritings which causes both infraclass variance and correlative inter-class similarity measures which makes the recognition a difficult task to accomplish with considerable accuracy. To overcome this problem highly abstract and invariant image feature are needs to be used for classification.

Figure 3.5: Commercial Product

Handwritten recognition can be done in two ways viz online and offline. The offline is recognition system performed after the digits are digitized. On the other hand, online recognition system can maintain real time information such as stroke. It is generally written on a pressure sensitive surface from which the stroke is preserved [1]. Off-line handwriting recognition is the process to translate digital image of handwritten text into machine editable text. Several recognition methodologies of Recognition of English, Latin, Arabic, Chinese scripts are extensively reviewed in [1], [2], [3], [4].

Telugu is the Dravidian language and is third most popular script in India [5]. It is also an official language of the southern Indian popularly used in state, Andhra Pradesh and its neighboring states. It is similar to the Kannada language. Telugu is a syllabic language and represents a complete syllable. Forally, there are 10 numerals, 18 vowels, 36 consonants, and three dual symbols. The challenging part of Indian handwritten character recognition is shape similarities among different characters. Handwritten recognition is very complex as there is a tiny variation in writing, which leads to great complex in recognition. The handwritten style of an individual different in size and shape which leads various numerals leads to similar shape. India is a multilingual and multi-script country comprising of twenty-five official languages [6], namely Assamese, Bangla, Bodo, Dogri, English, Gujarati, Hindi, Konkani, Kannada, Kashmiri, Malayalam, Maithili, Manipuri, Marathi, Nepali, Oriya, Punjabi, Rajasthani, Santali, Sanskrit, Sindhi, Tamil, Telugu and Urdu. Recognition of handwritten Indian scripts is more complicated than Roman script because of the presence of compound characters and vowel modifiers.

To recognize optical characters, features are extracted from every numeral that is captured. Each numeral has its own pattern in certain class. As may advancement in the optical character recognition, still the demand is high among research community. Earlier methods for recognition of handwritten character include directional distance features [7], gradient-based features [8], wavelet-based features [9], pixel distance features [10], and convexhull-based features [11].

In recent times, with the help Deep Learning (DL) the recognition of objects has more advancement. However, to discriminate the features is not understood well for various languages. This needs to investigate and identify newer patterns with less complexity algorithms that can classify accurately for complex style of handwritten characters.

Figure 3.6: Stages of Hand Reorganization System

3.5 Proposed CNN Model:

Here different Content/characters detected and isolated from given input samples network training is carried out using a CNN which is empowered to learn the distinct morphological patterns of all different classes with some finite discriminations. A convolutional neural network consists of several convolutional layers with appropriate activation functions and parameters as follows:

Where w is a set of convolution kernels,

and B is a bias.

At each layer, the input I is convolved N numbers of kernels $w = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_N\}$ and associated biases $B = \{B_1, B_2, \dots, B_N\}$. During the convolution operation, a new feature map I_{mid} is generated at each layer.

An activation function is formulated from each of these feature maps to carry out non-linear transform over the input.

The process is involved in each layer is formulated by using Eqn. (3.2) as shown below:

$$I_{kCL} = g(w * I_{kCL-1} + B_{kCL-1}) \quad \dots (3.2)$$

Where here, '*' the convolution operation and g denote the activation function.

CL refers to the total number of convolution layers in the CNN network.

Figure 3.7: sample MNIST dataset

In general pre-processing plays a significant role in CNN based handwritten recognition process. To formulate the input images into the most suitable form which can be easily used to learn the potential information is an essential task that needs to be accomplished before the network learning. Here gradient information's are extracted from input sample images with variance ranges from 0.2-0.5 as shown in Fig 3.7.the geometrical information available from gradient output is used for better normalization over labeled data and optimal discrimination among Content/characters and digits which are similar in appearance in handwritten format. Here sample images from MNIST dataset images were decomposed into a fixed image of size 28×28 . And hidden layers with 28 kernel/filter/patches are used with two different kernel sizes of 3×3 and 5×5 for extracting pixel and geometric features from input sample images. At each layer, all morphological and pixel information from input images is converted into neurons interconnections during the learning process. The concept of padding is also introduced in the proposed CNN architecture to get maximum accuracy. Here Padding is used to control the shrinking of the output of each convolution layer.

Figure 3.8: ROI for isolating the Content/characters

3.6 Result & Discussions:

As handwritten images are two-tone images with the character in the foreground, the preprocessing step involves size normalization, binarization and the extraction of boundary/edge pixels. Then, a chord is drawn from each boundary pixel to all other boundary pixels. For N number of boundary pixels, the total number of available chords is $N(N - 1)/2$. However, we discard those chords whose locus lies totally or partially inside the character region. The remaining chords are termed as the external chords (Fig. 1). The term ‘external’ is used since the chords are situated outside the foreground region. In recent years, the perception driven algorithms are observed to be the active field of research not just in generic object detection, but in pattern recognition and handwritten OCR too [38–40]. The philosophy is that classification systems aspiring for humanlike recognition accuracy must be able to detect the perceptually significant object parts as a human vision does. We observe that a set of parallel external chords is able to capture the perceptual shape parts effectively. This leads to exploring the possibility of representing a handwritten character pattern in terms of external symmetry axes constellation constituted from the symmetric bifurcation of such chords. These external symmetry axes uniquely represent the visually relevant parts of a character image and hence, show perceptual significance. From the experiments of Hoffman et al. [41–42], it has categorically been postulated that human vision puts highest weightage to fully convex parts such as closed curve or near-closed primitives collectively termed as closures, followed by other shape parts like bends, protrusions and straight parts (limbs). We therefore develop the second stage of our recognition by detecting perceptual closure parts of a character which discriminates two or more look-alike classes. The combination of visually significant external symmetry axes and perceptual closures motivates the character recognition approach proposed in this paper. This approach has several advantages: first, it does not require explicit parsing or decomposition algorithms; second, it works without skeleton pruning [43] or contour smoothing by DCE [44]; thirdly there is no need for optimization and dynamic programming and hence, low in computational complexity.

3.6.1 Experimental Setups:

To validate the performance metrics of the proposed deep learning framework in both handwritten digit and character recognition different learning parameters are used in the convolutional neural network which can produce optimal recognition accuracy and computational time. The network training parameter includes the learning rate of 0.01 and

maximum epoch counts of 5. And CNN layers also include hyper-parameters which include kernel size (1–5), stride (1–3), dilation (1–2), and padding (1–2). Each of these parameters offers a different level of explorations about potential information like edges and corners from the input images in the hidden layers of the CNN, which also helps to normalize the data learned and needs to be processed at the subsequent layers for the final feature map generation. The first observation from Table 1 shows the importance of improved learning with the extended number of hidden layers. As compared to 3 layers CNN architecture inclusion of additional layers offers significant improvement in overall recognition accuracy. In particular, the discrimination level among inter-class similarity and consistency over intraclass variations was also optimally obtained in the 4-layer CNN model.

Figure 3.9: Direct sample image from MNIST

Figure 3.10: Pre-processed sample image from MNIST using gradient measure

The handwritten recognition system comprises of the following steps:

- Step 1.** To collect benchmark handwritten digit and character images from the MNIST datasets.
- Step 2.** By Class: In this work, 62 different classes are used which include digits [0–9], lowercase letters [a–z], and uppercase letters [A–Z].
- Step 3.** To select 10 images from each class to formulate the training set.
- Step 4.** To apply gradient measures as a pre-processing technique to explore the boundary details over the training dataset.
- Step 5.** To formulate the CNN network model using three hidden layers and carried out a training process.
- Step 6.** To use a learned model for the classification of digits and Content/characters.
- Step 7.** To validate the performance metrics using classification accuracy.

Figure 3.11: External chords.

Figure 3.12: External symmetry axes and the corresponding boundary segments

As handwritten images are two-tone images with the character in the foreground, the preprocessing step involves size normalization, binarization and the extraction of boundary/edge pixels. Then, a chord is drawn from each boundary pixel to all other boundary pixels. For N number of boundary pixels, the total number of available chords is $N(N - 1)/2$. However, we discard those chords whose locus lies totally or partially inside the character region. The remaining chords are termed as the external chords (Fig. 1). The term ‘external’ is used since the chords are situated outside the foreground region. Training and recognition during training phase, a feature matrix for each character class ($z = 1, 2, \dots, Z$) is created and stored from a pool of sample training images. For M number of images per character class which are randomly selected in the database for training, the feature matrix will be of size $72 \times M$ (Fig. 8). The proposed recognition consists of two stages. First, when an unknown character image is to be recognized, the external symmetry axes are extracted and two histograms of orientation bins are computed and binary coded to generate the BESAC

feature. A Boolean XOR ($\oplus$) operation of the unknown feature vector (f) with the individual columns of the training feature matrices (Fz) is performed for matching with BESAC features. A matching metric (d_m^z) of an unknown image feature vector f is measured from the m^{th} training image of character class. This is nothing but the Hamming Distance (HD) used as a measure of dissimilarity: $d_m^z = M \times \text{HD}(Fz_m, f) = \sum_{m=1}^M |Fz_m - f|$; $\forall z = 1, 2, \dots, Z$ (10) these matching metric values are sorted so as to obtain the highest five matching (i.e. lowest values). If all the metric minima correspond to a single class, the unknown character is recognized as that class; otherwise, the detected classes are considered for the second stage. This particular binary feature matching operation is very fast because of efficient implementation of the matching process in terms of elementary Boolean operators acting in parallel. Even if the number of character templates is large, the inherent parallelism of the matching process is exploited for the sake of speed to achieve fast recognition. The effectiveness of the binary matching is evident from the similar technique proposed in very successful applications such as iris recognition in

Figure 3.13: Recognition flow diagram.

Table 3.1: Performance comparison of proposed handwritten recognition using different hybrid CNN parameters

Model	Layer	Kernel size (k)	Stride (s)	Dilation (d)	Padding (p)	Recognition accuracy		
						Digit (0-9)	Lower case(a-z)	Upper case (A-Z)
Mode1	Layer 3	3x3	2	2	2	94.67%	92.34%	93.29%
		5x5	3	1	1	92.89%	89.65%	92.87%
Mode2	Layer 4	3x3	2	2	2	95.54%	93.12%	94.1%
		5x5	3	1	1	93.56%	91.89%	93.6%

By relaxing the straightness criterion, a number of curved external axes are retained which cannot be approximated to a single orientation. Such axes fail to develop the desired constellation model which accounts for the high accuracy obtained. Contrarily, tightening the straightness criterion has the danger of losing out some important external axes that may otherwise correspond to a valid shape part. The experimentally chosen threshold therefore finds an optimal setting of this parameter.

Figure 3.14: Performance comparison of proposed handwritten recognition using different hybrid CNN parameters

Table 3.2: Performance comparison of proposed geometric driven handwritten recognition using gradient information

Model	Layer	Kernel size (k)	Recognition accuracy		
			Digit (0-9)	Lower case(a-z)	Upper case (A-Z)
Direct learning from the input sample	Layer 4	3x3	95.54%	93.12%	94.1%
Gradient processed sample	Layer 4	3x3	97.34%	95.23%	97.1%

3.6.2 Data Acquisition

To evaluate the performance metrics of the proposed hybrid CNN model, experiments are conducted in the MNIST benchmark dataset which includes both letters and digits. The training sets are formulated with 25 images for each class. All training samples are processed using a gradient with variance level varied from 0.2-0.4 for finite boundary detailed exploration as shown in Figure. 3.12.

Figure 3.15: Handwritten character recognition and annotation output

To evaluate the performance of the proposed HCR model for efficient character recognition the simulation experiment considers both samples from datasets and self-build handwritten Content/characters. Here for each evaluation, all individual's content/characters are randomly distributed all over the region and the experimental results evaluated both ROI selection using binary morphological operations and successive network classification separately.

3.7 State-Of-The-Art Comparison

To validate the performance metrics and associated recognition accuracy measurement of the proposed CNN framework comparative analyzes includes performance comparison with two prominent methods using the MNIST benchmark dataset. In Ghadekar et al. (2018) [19]) the authors used a multi-class support vector machine (SVM) for character recognition which includes two transform domain features were used namely discrete cosine transform (DCT) and discrete wavelet transform (DWT). This ML approach showed recognition accuracy of 89.51% and 97.74% for letters and digits respectively. Here it is noted that transform domain features are not sufficient to incorporate useful discriminative characteristics of different letters as compared to digit classifications. Moreover, intraclass variations are very less for all digits which is most common for letters for both upper and lower cases along with inter-class similarities. Cavalin et al. (2018) [20]) introduced the CNN framework for improved learning from letters which showed superior classification accuracy of 93.63% which is outperform the existing ML approach for letter recognition. So many techniques were used in many existing learning methods for maximizing the recognition accuracy of MNIST. As compared to other competitive DL models proposed CNN method has superior recognition accuracy of 94.8% and 99.7% for letters and digits respectively. And the proposed model is also tested with self-build real-time handwritten images which give around 89.47% using 4-layer CNN.

Table 3.3: Performance comparison of proposed CNN model

Technique	Letters	Digits
DWT-DCT + SVM (Ghadekar et al. (2018)) [19]	89.51%	97.74%
CNN (Cavalin et al. (2018)) [20]	93.63%	99.46%
Proposed CNN model	94.8%	99.7%

Figure 3.16: Performance comparison of proposed CNN model

3.8 Summary:

This paper attempted at creating an improved deep learning framework for handwritten recognition which includes both Content/characters and digits. By using an adaptive variance-based gradient formulation is used to explore the boundary details of each individual. The difference in the style of the handwritten scripts is efficiently learned using CNN with multiple hidden layers. Self-build samples were also considered for experimental analyzes to validate the performance metrics of the developed DL-HCR methodology. An acceptable detection rate of more than 90% was attained across all different classes during performance validation. The efficiency of gradient driven CNN modeling handwritten character recognition showed improved system performance over benchmark HCR datasets.

Chapter-4

A MIXTURE OF MLPNN/HMM DEMONSTRATES THE PROCEDURE FOR ONLINE HINDI WRITING RECOGNITION

4.1 Overview:

This chapter demonstrates a mixture of the MLPNN/HMM model for operational Hindi writing recognition. The planned structure is proposed on behalf of HMMs and various-Layer Perceptron Neural Linkages. Signal of input is generated toward uninterrupted knocks named segments constructed proceeding of the Elliptical approach through scrutinizing the extremisms arguments of the rounded rapidity outline. The linkage of neural accomplished through subdivision near relative evidence stays castoff near-abstract course atmosphere prospects. Proposed outcomes of that system remain translated through HMMs towards run after attractiveness of equal credit. Now appraisals are scheduled to DBMs Hindi database which proficient 97.8% attractiveness appreciation exactness that signifies statistically significantly imperative trendy evaluation through attractiveness appreciation exactitudes attained after advanced online Hindi systems. Developing a mixture of the MLPNN/HMM model for operational Hindi writing recognition. Based on the proposed model that system remains translated through HMMs towards run after attractiveness of equal credit. Now appraisals are scheduled to DBMs Hindi database which proficient 97.8% attractiveness appreciation exactness that signifies statistically significantly imperative trendy evaluation through attractiveness appreciation exactitudes attained after advanced online Hindi systems. A new conceptual of mixture of the MLPNN/HMM model has been proposed for operations of Hindi writing recognition techniques based on Perception Neural Linkages.

4.2 Introduction A Mixture Of MLPNN/HMM

Imitating humanoid capability trendy mainframe suggestions remain motionless stimulating notwithstanding the enormous developments that happened fashionable the park of intelligence derives in an artificial solicitation. Moreover, the script appreciation sphere through the dual twigs disconnected then operational takes placed in the concentration on behalf of previous periods. Authentic consequences remain actual encouraging plus rendering towards nonfiction of appreciation accurateness charges conveyed through countless organizations be situated above 85%. Aimed at Hindi calligraphy then owing toward the situation lettering physiognomies that container remains enlightened trendy supplementary

minutiae cutting-edge [1], unevenness, touching typescripts, attendance of strings, accents custom, moreover state-owned for less in terms of development besides that requested by way of resolved badly-behaved.

Numerous methodologies have been industrialized then Concealed HMMs models which are the best innovative tools are using this generation [2-5]. Moreover remain numerical representations that adopt tremendously well-organized trendy the arena for involuntary language gratitude. For achievement takes interested fresh efforts toward contrivance HMMs trendy atmosphere gratitude for connected before disconnected. Thus custom trendy script appreciation ampule remain clarified through the competence toward section then identify unwritten calligraphy that's build up selfsame multifaceted after consuming obvious approaches. Numerous connections related to neural constructions consume stayed rummage-sale similarly [6-8]. Therefore, remained rummage-sale essentially aimed at inaccessible atmosphere appreciation. However, it's mainly owing to previously originated numbers desirable on behalf of teaching [9]. Therefore, a mixture technique uniting the dual kinds of the overhead statistics appears towards remaining gifted toward profits recompenses for various outsized as well as setting demonstrating through the connectivity of neural though benefitting since for Monrovia arrangement exhibiting [10-22]. The aforementioned efforts happen popular for nonfiction besides were selfsame effective on behalf of together operational and disconnected script appreciation [11-26]. Therefore, connectivity in terms of neural is being used for getting the results comment prospects used for HMMs. For the emerging field of sectors, development is working towards feature in dissimilar periods for the organization then towards deliberates various encounters for every period. Lastly it determination shot for challenging outcomes grounded proceeding for script data [14-15]. The main objective of the proposed work is to mixture MLPNN/HMM scheme for Hindi written calligraphy appreciation wherever results productivity likelihood compression purposes for the disconnected HMM's situations stay approached through the MLP network. In addition, by using connectivity in terms of neural is being used for getting the results comment prospects used for HMMs. For the emerging field of sectors, development is working towards feature in dissimilar periods for the organization then towards deliberates various encounters for every period. This resolution remained near revenue compensations for associated proper control of connectivity of neural although earning since the Monrovia categorization demonstrating. To circumvent a sophisticated deciphering complication

primarily owing toward custom for together differences, the MLPNN remained impartial charity proceeding with the exercise fragment for the proposed structure.

Figure 4.1: Generation of Handwriting Applying RNN with Mixture Density Network

Figure 4.2: Improving Offline Handwritten Text Recognition with Hybrid HMM/ANN Models

4.3 Hybrid HMM/ANN Model: An Approaches Methods

This section exists of planned arrangements in construction counting for processed then standardization stages depicted in figure 1. Formerly the mined topographies stay labeled rendering towards for elliptic of beta demonstrating method. For separation insolence, secondhand remains portrayed besides lastly, that comprehensive for appreciation organization which rummage-sale grounded proceeding of recognition and isolated HMMs.

Figure 4.3: Illustration of established structure

4.3.1 Steps for process:

Process stage stays important now slightly writing appreciation for development towards excluding in sound engendered once obtaining in motion proceeding in arithmetical strategies then toward handgrip in numerous swiftness plus forms on inscription through standardizing in script magnitudes. In Major perpendicular measurements from the handwriting, appearances remain attuned toward getting standardized scope calligraphy. In subsequent ladders recapitulate in process A.

4.3.1.1 Maximum assessment m remains calculated:

$M = \max(\max_a - \min_a, \max_c - \min_c)$; B. Aimed at every a, b of course writing, that modification in original standards by this calculation;

$$a_{norm}=128*((a-min_a)/M); b_{norm}=128*((b-min_b)/M); \dots (4.1)$$

Everywhere 128 remains a verge data which is immobile afterward numerous investigational examinations. Formerly, in Chebyshev additional category low-slung permission filter is used as limit regularity for a value of 14Hz then a range of sifting gap R is 6 useful arranged in the standardized course towards eradicating for sound familiarized through chronological plus solid sample shown in diagram 2.

Figure 4.4: Little – authorization sifting aimed at sound removal plus route flattening

4.3.2 Insertion for chain

In a presentation for established appreciation organization be contingent seriously happening in what way fit of diverse inscription panaches remain demonstrated. Dissimilar script to Latin, Hindi linguistic takes a great conventional for typescripts conditional scheduled for situations inside in expression [1]. Therefore, identifying an assumed atmosphere remains an additional problematic mission. Toward excerpt in chin trajectories commencing for standardized calligraphy, superior methods of the elliptical process are present [16]. The purpose is to decompose in indication keen on sections. Every section remains distinct equally unremitting calligraphy knock amongst dual boundaries opinions on behalf of upwards else downwards instants [16].

Following conventional that dig up topographies container remain separated addicted to dual programmers. IN principal course contains self-motivated topographies put in on behalf of all opinion seeing in rapidity outline through admiration towards period over reviewing in extremism opinions demonstrating limited most as well as lowest for rounded speed sign of script then the interior facts. Additional lesson revenues stationary topographies on behalf of the calligraphy course. All section route remains demonstrated in an ellipse of semicircles for example explained trendy [16].

Figure 4.5: The Beta model

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n K_i \beta(t, q, p, t_0, t_1) \quad \dots (4.2)$$

$$\beta(t, q, p, t_0, t_1) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{t-t_0}{t_c-t_0}\right)^p \left(\frac{t_1-t}{t_1-t_c}\right)^q & \text{if } t \in [t_0, t_1] \\ 0 & \text{if not} \end{cases} \quad \dots (4.3)$$

The rapidity outline of P: This one remains limitation autonomous of the rapidity outline decisive the Beta occupation figure K: largeness of the meaning Beta V_{in} : in preliminary liveliness of commencement for intermission ΔT which disintegrates finished interval. Industrialized live lines toward behavior to incessant knock pending of conclusion at interval ΔT .

Figure 4.6: Rapidity outline –flight communication

4.4 Segmentation

Figure 4.7: Radicalism points recognition procedure

A knocks congregation machinery remainders formerly desirable toward a quotation in dissimilar typescripts constituting various expressions. Illustrations of knocks congregation consequences remain obtainable in cutting-edge Tabular 4.1.

Table 4.1. Knocks congregation on sequences aimed at type scripts “ए”, “बी” and “सी”

Character	Position	Strokes number					
		2	3	4	5	6	7
ए	Be	☒	☒				
	Mi		☒				
	En			☒	☒		☒
	Iso		☒				
बी	Be				☒	☒	
	Mi	☒				☒	☒
	En		☒			☒	☒
	Iso					☒	
सी	Be	☒	☒				
	Mi		☒	☒			
	En			☒	☒	☒	☒
	Iso		☒	☒		☒	

4.5 The Engine Of Recognition

4.5.1 Secreted design of Markov:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{W} &= \arg \max P(w|X) = \arg \max \frac{P(w)P(X|w)}{P(X)} \\ &= \arg \max P(w)P(X|w) \end{aligned}$$

...(4.3)

4.5.2 Multilayer Perceptron:

Figure 4.8: Network of neural connection

Where

- $p = [p_1 p_2 \dots p_R]^T$ is the input vector
- $w = [w_{1,1} w_{1,2} \dots w_{1,R}]^T$ is the weights vector.
- $$\begin{aligned}
 n &= \sum_{j=1}^R w_{1,j} p_j - b \\
 &= w_{1,1} p_1 + w_{1,2} p_2 + \dots + w_{1,R} p_R - b \\
 &= w^T p^T - b
 \end{aligned}$$
... (4.4)

Every source of neurons consumes unique production that creates remains in outcome for transmission meaning to the prejudiced amount for the situation involvements.

4.6 Mixture of MLPNN/HMM process:

Systems of neural canister stay measured arithmetical process underneath convinced circumstances, through providing production for different prospects. Therefore, the situation remains stimulating toward association in individual measurements for NN and HMM creating a novel well-organized appreciation coordination stimulated through the binary procedure. Primarily query remains exactly how on the way to association binary changed process, particularly in a way that an organization cannot modest toward contrivance for the

reason that various quantity of limitations toward correct plus it's a great number of exercise statistics essential toward guarantee in comprehensive prototypical steps. Popular methods for generating these steps are given below.

Figure 4.9: Projected mixture of NN and HMM appreciation construction

In this projected appreciation classification remains NN chin removed constructed near transform session possibility approximations towards subsequent for chin trajectory appropriate on behalf of succeeding HMM procedure. The projected scheme remains collected for a network of neural processes. Every lesson for encryption attractiveness resembles the single process of neural. Above construction for the process of neural can accessible reference diagram4.

All connections of neural remained proficient through some typical backbone circulation procedure through preparation limitations like amount: $i = 0.01$ and impetus feature: $a = 24$; then iterative amount meant for preparation: periods = 4000 [18].

Following NN subsequent prospects $P(S|A)$ is separated through the preceding formal prospects $P(S)$ popular instruction towards estimated in thought prospects for HMM.

$$P(X|S) \approx \frac{P(S|X)}{P(S)}$$

where

$$-\log p(X|S) = -\log p(S|X) + \alpha \log p(S) \quad (3) \quad \dots(4.5)$$

Table 4.2: Normal Appreciation proportions by dissimilar encryption dimensions then numeral of situations in each model

Size of Code					
	2	3	4	5	6
126	72.23%	80.12%	82.12%	83.35%	78.56%
256	80.12%	86.31%	91.12%	90.27%	88.96%
512	82.23%	87.15%	87.14%	86.19%	85.80%

Figure 4.10: Regular Appreciation duties expending dissimilar code proportions than the number of conditions each prototypical step

4.7 Investigational Scenery

In investigation stayed directed by the DBMs catalog that contains 837 dissimilar brands for connected names. In particular, each folder remains accessible in cutting-edge tabular 4.3.

Table 4.3: Different DABs values

Set	Files	Sub-words	character	writer
1	5036	7546	40600	58
2	5091	7869	41516	39
3	5032	7580	40312	26
4	4418	6458	32456	7
5	1000	1593	8741	9
6	1000	1526	8125	4

Table 4.4: Consequences for dissimilar arrangement sharpening in results of different sets in DBMs in 4-6

Systems	Set 4			Set 5			Set 6		
	Top1	Top5	Top10	Top1	Top5	Top10	Top1	Top5	Top10
Basic MLP system	89.97%	71.14%	71.14%	69.52%	69.52%	69.52%	70.52%	70.52%	98.97%
Continuous HMM system	71.14%	91.89%	91.89%	90.15%	90.71%	91.23%	70.52%	91.87%	91.87%
Discrete HMM system	91.26 %	93.25%	93.25%	91.62%	92.78%	92.78%	90.36%	92.78%	92.78%
MLP/HMM system	96.45%	97.08%	97.58%	96.12%	97.51%	97.51%	95.20%	96.86%	97.27%
Best ICDAR 2011 system	98.02%	98.98 %	98.98 %	98.18%	99.18%	99.18%	98.45%	98.97 %	91.23%

Designed for the preparation segment, select toward usage segment typescripts in its place of by a folder that inaccessible typescripts toward improved speech difficulties of appeals concatenation trendy a contribution discussion. Consequently, our proposed design of 5000 confrontations having selected haphazardly after the principal circles of three of DBMs. Finally gotten 288960 section knocks that consume inoculated toward the NN near to accumulate dissimilar Hindi typescripts carcasses that would remain recycled advanced

through the HMM analyzers. Furthermore, knocks congregation instrument remained administered then somewhat certain ladders stayed achieved physically toward safeguard decent parts organization. Cutting-edge for assessment stage, a proposed design implemented in structure happening in the box 4, 5 then 6 of DBMs. Towards appraise in presentation for planned organization, and associated towards typical MLP scheme plus near disconnected HMM then incessant HMM appreciation scheme. Obtained preparation statistics remained similar aimed at together schemes.

4.8 Results And Discussion

Accomplished appreciation fallouts remain existing now in the succeeding tabular 4. Major, this one container remains understood, which be separate arrangement outclasses in incessant HMMs. Following approves through preceding everything cutting-edge the works by means of in [11-22]. In notification correspondingly for these consequences obtainable through the NN classification remain meaningfully subordinate. The following predominantly owing to the absence of statistics throughout in knowledge chapter. Associated toward the normal NN arrangement, toward disconnected HMM organization besides toward incessant HMM organization, projected coordination offerings an enhanced appreciation proportion aimed at thrice examination groups.

Figure 4.11: Consequences of dissimilar structures scheduled in set 4-6

From the obtained data of our mixture NN based HMM coordination remains somewhat minor to individuals accomplished through the major arrangement which takes contended in place of connected Hindi writing appreciation opposition [20]. Also, the developed method is able to stand charity on behalf of presentations allocating through the exposed dictionary for the situation remains appeal constructed.

4.9 Summary

Developed work projected trendy a mixture MLPNN/HMM scheme for Hindi written calligraphy appreciation wherever results productivity likelihood compression purposes for the disconnected HMM's situations stay approached through the MLP network. This resolution remained near revenue compensations for associated proper control of connectivity of neural although earning since the Monrovia categorization demonstrating. To circumvent a sophisticated deciphering complication primarily owing toward custom for together differences, the MLPNN remained impartial charity proceeding with the exercise fragment for the proposed structure. Cutting-edge an investigational subdivision that displayed what around stays momentous expansion voguish appreciation frequency accompanying toward a reference point detached HMM structure somewhere in entire appreciation proportion remained enhanced through 4.25% by the projected mixture methodology. The forthcoming effort contains for enlightening in genuine projected coordination succeeding dual-core instructions:

1. Feature insertion plus
2. Hard appreciation apparatus. Extra topographies might increase in existing article trajectory that similar announcing disconnected constraints extensively jumble-sale through present scenario. Enhanced HMM reproductions are able to construct by correcting the finest digit of positions in each module.

Chapter-5

RESULT & DISCUSSIONS

5.1 Experimental Setups:

To validate the performance metrics of the proposed deep learning framework in both handwritten digit and character recognition different learning parameters are used in the convolutional neural network which can produce optimal recognition accuracy and computational time. The network training parameter includes the learning rate of 0.01 and maximum epoch counts of 5. And CNN layers also include hyper-parameters which include kernel size (1–5), stride (1–3), dilation (1–2), and padding (1–2). Each of these parameters offers a different level of explorations about potential information like edges and corners from the input images in the hidden layers of the CNN, which also helps to normalize the data learned and needs to be processed at the subsequent layers for the final feature map generation. The first observation from Table 1 shows the importance of improved learning with the extended number of hidden layers. As compared to 3 layers CNN architecture inclusion of additional layers offers significant improvement in overall recognition accuracy. In particular, the discrimination level among inter-class similarity and consistency over infraclass variations was also optimally obtained in the 4-layer CNN model.

Figure 5.1: Database of image input from MNIST

Figure 5.2: Pre-processed sample image from MNIST using gradient measure

Table 5.1: Performance comparison of hybrid CNN parameters

Model	Layer	Kernel size (k)	Stride (s)	Dilation (d)	Padding (p)	Recognition accuracy		
						Digit (0-9)	Lower case(a-z)	Upper case (A-Z)
Mode1	Layer 3	3x3	2	2	2	94.67%	92.34%	93.29%
		5x5	3	1	1	92.89%	89.65%	92.87%
Mode2	Layer 4	3x3	2	2	2	95.54%	93.12%	94.1%
		5x5	3	1	1	93.56%	91.89%	93.6%

Figure 5.3: Performance comparison of proposed handwritten recognition using different hybrid CNN parameters

Table 5.2: Performance comparison of proposed Method

Model	Layer	Kernel size (k)	Recognition accuracy		
			Digit (0-9)	Lower case(a-z)	Upper case (A-Z)
Direct learning from the input sample	Layer 4	3x3	95.54%	93.12%	94.1%
Gradient processed sample	Layer 4	3x3	97.34%	95.23%	97.1%

Figure 5.4: Performance comparison of proposed Method

5.2 State-Of-The-Art Comparison

To validate the performance metrics and associated recognition accuracy measurement of the proposed CNN framework comparative analyzes includes performance comparison with two prominent methods using the MNIST benchmark dataset. In Ghadekar et al. (2018) [19]) the authors used a multi-class support vector machine (SVM) for character recognition which includes two transform domain features were used namely discrete cosine transform (DCT) and discrete wavelet transform (DWT). This ML approach showed recognition accuracy of 89.51% and 97.74% for letters and digits respectively. Here it is noted that transform domain features are not sufficient to incorporate useful discriminative characteristics of different letters as compared to digit classifications. Moreover, intraclass variations are very less for all digits which is most common for letters for both upper and lower cases along with inter-class similarities. Cavalin et al. (2018) [20]) introduced the CNN framework for improved learning from letters which showed superior classification accuracy of 93.63% which is outperform the existing ML approach for letter recognition. So many techniques were used in many existing learning methods for maximizing the recognition accuracy of MNIST. As compared to other competitive DL models proposed CNN method has superior recognition accuracy of

94.8% and 99.7% for letters and digits respectively. And the proposed model is also tested with self-build real-time handwritten images which give around 89.47% using 4-layer CNN.

Table 5.3: Performance comparison of proposed CNN model

Technique	Letters	Digits
DWT-DCT + SVM (Ghadekar et al. (2018)) [19]	89.51%	97.74%
CNN (Cavalin et al. (2018)) [20]	93.63%	99.46%
Proposed CNN model	94.8%	99.7%

Figure 5.5: Performance comparison of proposed CNN model

5.3: Mlpnn/Hmm Demonstrates The Procedure For Online Hindi Writing Recognition:

Accomplished appreciation fallouts remain existing now in the succeeding tabular 4. Major, this one container remains understood, which be separate arrangement outclasses in incessant HMMs. Following approves through preceding everything cutting-edge the works by means of in [11-22]. In notification correspondingly for these consequences obtainable through the NN classification remain meaningfully subordinate. The following predominantly owing to the absence of statistics throughout in knowledge chapter. Associated toward the normal NN arrangement, toward disconnected HMM organization besides toward incessant HMM organization, projected coordination offerings an enhanced appreciation proportion aimed at thrice examination groups.

Figure 5.6: Different DA values

Figure 5.7: Structures schedule din set 4-6

From the obtained data of our mixture NN based HMM coordination remains somewhat minor to individuals accomplished through the major arrangement which takes contended in place of connected Hindi writing appreciation opposition. Also, the developed method is able to stand charity on behalf of presentations allocating through the exposed dictionary for the situation remains appeal constructed.

5.4: Summary

- To validate the performance metrics of the proposed deep learning framework in both handwritten digit and character recognition different learning parameters are used.
- Performance comparison of proposed CNN model has been done.
- Structures schedule din set 4-6 has been analyzed.
- Performance comparison of proposed handwritten recognition using different hybrid CNN parameters has been determining.

Chapter-6

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE

6.1 Conclusions

- This work attempted at creating an improved deep learning framework for handwritten recognition which includes both Content/characters and digits. By using an adaptive variance-based gradient formulation is used to explore the boundary details of each individual.
- The difference in the style of the handwritten scripts is efficiently learned using CNN with multiple hidden layers. Self-build samples were also considered for experimental analyzes to validate the performance metrics of the developed DL-HCR methodology.
- An acceptable detection rate of more than 90% was attained across all different classes during performance validation. The efficiency of gradient driven CNN modeling handwritten character recognition showed improved system performance over benchmark HCR datasets.
- Developed work projected trendy a mixture MLPNN/HMM scheme for Hindi written calligraphy appreciation wherever results productivity likelihood compression purposes for the disconnected HMM's situations stay approached through the MLP network.
- This resolution remained near revenue compensations for associated proper control of connectivity of neural although earning since the Monrovia categorization demonstrating. To circumvent a sophisticated deciphering complication primarily owing toward custom for together differences, the MLPNN remained impartial charity proceeding with the exercise fragment for the proposed structure.
- Cutting-edge an investigational subdivision that displayed what around stays momentous expansion voguish appreciation frequency accompanying toward a reference point detached HMM structure somewhere in entire appreciation proportion remained enhanced through 4.25% by the projected mixture methodology.
- The forthcoming effort contains for enlightening in genuine projected coordination succeeding dual-core instructions: 1. feature insertion plus, 2. hard appreciation apparatus

- Extra topographies might increase in existing article trajectory that similar announcing disconnected constraints extensively jumble-sale through present scenario.
- Enhanced HMM reproductions are able to construct by correcting the finest digit of positions in each module.

6.2 Future Scope

- Seven approaches of feature extraction namely, box method, diagonal distance method, mean and gradient operation, standard deviation, center of gravity and edge detection can be used to develop an off-line character recognition system.
- Two different recognition networks can build namely Adaptive MLP classifier without feature reduction and Adaptive MLP classifier with feature reduction.
- The network can be trained and tested on the CEDAR CDROM-1 dataset.
- It can be concluded from the experimental results that the network which uses GA based feature selection method improves overall performance of the recognition system in terms of speed and storage requirement.
- It has also been verified that the proposed adaptive MLP Neural Network works as a better classifier and provides better accuracy.

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A Mixture of MLPNN/HMM to Demonstrate the Procedure for Online Hindi Writing Recognition

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A Mixture of MLPNN/HMM to Demonstrate the Procedure for Online Hindi Writing Recognition

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: This presented work demonstrates a mixture of the MLPNN/HMM model for operational Hindi writing recognition. The planned structure is proposed on behalf of HMMs and various-Layer Perceptron Neural Linkages. Signal of input is generated toward uninterrupted knocks named segments constructed proceeding of the Elliptical approach through scrutinizing the extremisms arguments of the rounded rapidity outline. The linkage of neural accomplished through subdivision near relative evidence stays castoff near-abstract course atmosphere prospects. Proposed outcomes of that system remain translated through HMMs towards run after attractiveness of equal credit. Now appraisals are scheduled to DBMs Hindi database which proficient 97.8% attractiveness appreciation exactness that signifies statistically significantly imperative trendy evaluation through attractiveness appreciation exactitudes attained after advanced online Hindi systems.

Design/Methodology/Approach: Developing a mixture of the MLPNN/HMM model for operational Hindi writing recognition.

Findings/Result: Based on the proposed model that system remains translated through HMMs towards run after attractiveness of equal credit. Now appraisals are scheduled to DBMs Hindi database which proficient 97.8% attractiveness appreciation exactness that signifies statistically significantly imperative trendy evaluation through attractiveness appreciation exactitudes attained after advanced online Hindi systems.

Originality/Value: A new conceptual mixture of the MLPNN/HMM model has been proposed for operations of Hindi writing recognition techniques based on Perceptron Neural Linkages.

Paper Type: Conceptual Research.

Keywords: Hidden Markov Models MLP, Online Hindi Writing Recognition

1. INTRODUCTION :

Imitating humanoid capability trendy mainframe suggestions remain motionless stimulating notwithstanding the enormous developments that happened fashionable the park of intelligence derives in an artificial solicitation. Moreover, the script appreciation sphere through the dual twigs disconnected then operational takes placed in the concentration on behalf of previous periods. Authentic consequences remain actual encouraging plus rendering towards nonfiction of appreciation accurateness charges conveyed through countless organizations be situated above 85%. Aimed at Hindi calligraphy then owing toward the situation lettering physiognomies that container remains enlightened trendy supplementary minutiae cutting-edge [1], unevenness, touching typescripts, attendance of strings, accents custom, moreover state-owned for less in terms of development besides that requested by way of resolved badly-behaved.

Numerous methodologies have been industrialized then Concealed HMMs models which are the best innovative tools are using this generation [2-5]. Moreover, remain numerical representations that adopt tremendously well-organized trendy the arena for involuntary language gratitude. For achievement takes interested fresh efforts toward contrivance HMMs trendy atmosphere gratitude for connected before disconnected. Thus, custom trendy script appreciation ampule remains clarified through the

competence toward section then identify unwritten calligraphy that's build up selfsame multifaceted after consuming obvious approaches. Numerous connections related to neural constructions consume stayed rummage-sale similarly [6-8]. Therefore, remained rummage-sale essentially aimed at inaccessible atmosphere appreciation. However, it's mainly owing to previously originated numbers desirable on behalf of teaching [9]. Therefore, a mixture technique uniting the dual kinds of the overhead statistics appears towards remaining gifted toward profits recompenses for various outsized as well as setting demonstrating through the connectivity of neural though benefitting since for Monrovia arrangement exhibiting [10-22]. The aforementioned efforts happen popular for nonfiction besides were selfsame effective on behalf of together operational and disconnected script appreciation [11-26]. Therefore, connectivity in terms of neural is being used for getting the results comment prospects used for HMMs. For the emerging field of sectors, development is working towards feature in dissimilar periods for the organization then towards deliberate various encounters for every period. Lastly its determination shot for challenging outcomes grounded proceeding for script data [14-15].

2. OBJECTIVE OF THE PAPER :

The main objective of the proposed work is to mix MLPNN/HMM scheme for Hindi written calligraphy appreciation wherever results productivity likelihood compression purposes for the disconnected HMM's situations stay approached through the MLP network. In addition, by using connectivity in terms of neural is being used for getting the results comment prospects used for HMMs. For the emerging field of sectors, development is working towards feature in dissimilar periods for the organization then towards deliberate various encounters for every period. This resolution remained near revenue compensations for associated proper control of connectivity of neural although earning since the Monrovia categorization demonstrating. To circumvent a sophisticated deciphering complication primarily owing toward custom for together differences, the MLPNN remained impartial charity proceeding with the exercise fragment for the proposed structure.

3. APPROACHES METHODS :

This section exists of planned arrangements in construction counting for processed then standardization stages depicted in figure 1. Formerly the mined topographies stay labeled rendering towards for elliptic of beta demonstrating method. For separation insolence, secondhand remains portrayed besides lastly, that comprehensive for appreciation organization which rummage-sale grounded proceeding of recognition and isolated HMMs.

Fig. 1: Illustration of established structure

(1) Steps for process:

Process stage stays important now slightly writing appreciation for development towards excluding in sound engendered once obtaining in motion proceeding in arithmetical strategies then toward handgrip in numerous swiftness plus forms on inscription through standardizing in script magnitudes. In Major perpendicular measurements from the handwriting, appearances remain attuned toward getting standardized scope calligraphy. In subsequent ladders recapitulate in process A. Maximum assessment m remains calculated: $M = \max(\max_a - \min_a, \max_c - \min_c)$; B. Aimed at every a, b of course writing, that modification in original standards by this calculation;

$$a_{norm} = 128 * ((a - \min_a) / M); \quad b_{norm} = 128 * ((b - \min_b) / M);$$

Everywhere 128 remains a verge data which is immobile afterward numerous investigational examinations. Formerly, in Chebyshev additional category low-slung permission filter is used as limit regularity for a value of 14Hz then a range of sifting gap R is 6 useful arranged in the standardized course towards eradicating for sound familiarized through chronological plus solid sample shown in diagram 2.

Fig. 2: Little - authorization sifting aimed at sound removal plus route flattening

(2) Insertion for chain:

In a presentation for established appreciation organization be contingent seriously happening in what way fit of diverse inscription panaches remain demonstrated. Dissimilar script to Latin, Hindi linguistic takes a great conventional for typescripts conditional scheduled for situations inside in expression [1]. Therefore, identifying an assumed atmosphere remains an additional problematic mission. Toward excerpt in chin trajectories commencing for standardized calligraphy, superior methods of the elliptical process are present [16]. The purpose is to decompose in indication keen on sections. Every section remains distinct equally unremitting calligraphy knock amongst dual boundaries opinions on behalf of upwards else downwards instants [16].

Following conventional that dig up topographies' container remain separated addicted to dual programmers. IN principal course contains self-motivated topographies put in on behalf of all opinion seeing in rapidity outline through admiration towards period over reviewing in extremism opinions demonstrating limited most as well as lowest for rounded speed sign of script then the interior facts. Additional lesson revenues stationary topographies on behalf of the calligraphy course. All section route remains demonstrated in an ellipse of semicircles for example explained trendy [16].

Fig. 3: The Beta model

$$V(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n K_i \cdot \beta(t, q_i, p_i, t_{0i}, t_{1i}) \quad (1)$$

$$\beta(t, q, p, t_0, t_1) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{t-t_0}{t_c-t_0}\right)^p \left(\frac{t_1-t}{t_1-t_c}\right)^q & \text{if } t \in [t_0, t_1] \\ 0 & \text{if not} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The rapidity outline of P: this one remains limitation autonomous of the rapidity outline decide the Beta occupation figure K: largeness of the meaning Beta Vin: in preliminary liveliness of commencement for intermission ΔT which disintegrates finished interval. Industrialized liveliness toward behavior to incessant knock pending of conclusion at interval ΔT.

Fig. 4: rapidity outline –flight communication

4. SEGMENTATION :

Fig. 5: Radicalism points recognition procedure

A knocks congregation machinery remainders formerly desirable toward a quotation in dissimilar typescripts constituting various expressions. Illustrations of knocks congregation consequences remain obtainable in cutting-edge Table 1.

Table 1: Knocks congregation consequences aimed at typescripts “ए”, “बी” and “सी”

Character	Position	Strokes number					
		2	3	4	5	6	7
ए	Be	☒	☒				
	Mi		☒				
	En			☒	☒		☒
	Iso		☒				
बी	Be				☒	☒	
	Mi	☒				☒	☒
	En		☒			☒	☒
	Iso					☒	
सी	Be	☒	☒				
	Mi		☒	☒			
	En			☒	☒	☒	☒
	Iso		☒	☒		☒	

5. THE ENGINE OF RECOGNITION :

(1) Secreted design:

Secreted design Markov models (HMMs) are competent to segment besides to identify at the same time which is the main motive used for their instinctive handwriting appreciation systems. Primary approach for relating HMMs to handwriting recognition stayed initially interested by their achievement in speech recognition [9].

Intended for the examination of consecutive data, the procedure of HMMs for example arithmetical models can be considered the state-of-the-art [26]. In general, created on the supposition of a numerical model for the generation of the data to be investigated. The main purpose is to discovery the arrangement w which exploits the subsequent probability $P(w|X)$ of the character sequence specified the data X .

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{W} &= \arg \max P(w|X) = \arg \max \frac{P(w)P(X|w)}{P(X)} \\ &= \arg \max P(w)P(X|w) \end{aligned}$$

Where, input text sequence is X and recognizer must find the arrangement W of words which exploits the possibility $P(w) P(X | w)$. $P(w)$ is the prior possibility of the expression which is projected by the linguistic model. $P(X | w)$ is the statement probability projected by this language model.

(2) Multilayer Perceptron:

Fig. 6: Network of neural connection

Where

$p = [p_1 p_2 \dots p_r]^T$ is the input vector

$w = [w_{1,1} w_{1,2} \dots w_{1,R}]^T$ is the weights vector

$$n = \sum_{j=1}^R w_{1,j} p_j - b$$

$$= w_{1,1} p_1 + w_{1,2} p_2 + \dots + w_{1,R} p_R - b$$

$$= \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{p} - b \quad (3)$$

Every source of neurons consumes unique production that creates remains in outcome for transmission meaning to the prejudiced amount for the situation involvements.

(3) Mixture of MLPNN/HMM process:

Systems of neural canister stay measured arithmetical process underneath convinced circumstances, through providing production for different prospects. Therefore, the situation remains stimulating toward association in individual measurements for NN and HMM creating a novel well-organized appreciation coordination stimulated through the binary procedure. Primarily query remains exactly how on the way to association binary changed process, particularly in a way that an organization cannot modest toward contrivance for the reason that various quantity of limitations toward correct plus it's a great number of exercise statistics essential toward guarantee in comprehensive prototypical steps. Popular methods for generating these steps are given below.

Fig. 7: Projected mixture of NN and HMM appreciation construction

In this projected appreciation classification remains NN chin removed constructed near transform session possibility approximations towards subsequent for chin trajectory appropriate on behalf of succeeding HMM procedure. The projected scheme remains collected for a network of neural processes. Every lesson for encryption attractiveness resembles the single process of neural. Above construction for the process of neural can be accessible reference diagram 7.

All connections of neural remained proficient through some typical backbone circulation procedure through preparation limitations like amount: $i = 0.01$ and impetus feature: $a = 24$; then iterative amount meant for preparation: periods = 4000 [18].

Following NN subsequent prospects $P(S|A)$ is separated through the preceding formal prospects $P(S)$ popular instruction towards estimated in thought prospects for HMM.

$$P(X/S) \approx \frac{P(S/X)}{P(S)}$$

Where, $-\log P(X/S) = -\log P(S/X) + \alpha \log P(S)$ (4)

Table 2: Normal Appreciation proportions by dissimilar encryption dimensions then numeral of situations in each model

Size of Code	2	3	4	5	6
126	72.23%	80.12%	82.12%	83.35%	78.56%
256	80.12%	86.31%	91.12%	90.27%	88.96%
512	82.23%	87.15%	87.14%	86.19%	85.80%

Fig. 8: Regular Appreciation duties expending dissimilar code proportions than the number of conditions each prototypical step

6. INVESTIGATIONAL SCENERY :

In investigation stayed directed by the DBMs catalog that contains 837 dissimilar brands for connected names. In particular, each folder remains accessible in cutting-edge table 3.

Table 3: Different DABs values

Set	Files	Sub-words	character	writer
1	5036	7546	40600	58
2	5091	7869	41516	39
3	5032	7580	40312	26
4	4418	6458	32456	7
5	1000	1593	8741	9
6	1000	1526	8125	4

Table 4: Consequences for dissimilar arrangements happening in results of different sets in DBMs in 4-6

Systems	Set 4			Set 5			Set 6		
	Top1	Top5	Top10	Top1	Top5	Top10	Top1	Top5	Top10
Basic MLP system	89.97%	71.14%	71.14%	69.52%	69.52%	69.52%	70.52%	70.52%	98.97%
Continuous HMM system	71.14%	91.89%	91.89%	90.15%	90.71%	91.23%	70.52%	91.87%	91.87%
Discrete HMM system	91.26 %	93.25%	93.25%	91.62%	92.78%	92.78%	90.36%	92.78%	92.78%
MLP/HMM system	96.45%	97.08%	97.58%	96.12%	97.51%	97.51%	95.20%	96.86%	97.27%
Best ICDAR 2011 system	98.02%	98.98 %	98.98 %	98.18%	99.18%	99.18%	98.45%	98.97 %	91.23%

Designed for the preparation segment, select toward usage segment typescripts in its place of by a folder that inaccessible typescripts toward improved speech difficulties of appeals concatenation trendy a contribution discussion. Consequently, our proposed design of 5000 confrontations having selected haphazardly after the principal circles of three of DBMs. Finally gotten 288960 section knocks that consume inoculated toward the NN near to accumulate dissimilar Hindi typescripts carcasses that would remain recycled advanced through the HMM analyzers. Furthermore, knocks congregation instrument remained administered then somewhat certain ladders stayed achieved physically toward safeguard decent parts organization. Cutting-edge for assessment stage, a proposed design implemented in structure happening in the box 4, 5 then 6 of DBMs. Towards appraise in presentation for planned organization, and associated towards typical MLP scheme plus near disconnected HMM then incessant HMM appreciation scheme. Obtained preparation statistics remained similar aimed at together schemes.

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION :

Accomplished appreciation fallouts remain existing now in the succeeding table 4. Main, this one container remains understood, which be separate arrangement outclasses in incessant HMMs. Following approves through preceding everything cutting-edge the works by means of in [11-22]. In notification correspondingly for these consequences obtainable through the NN classification remain meaningfully subordinate. The following predominantly owing to the absence of statistics throughout in knowledge chapter. Associated toward the normal NN arrangement, toward disconnected HMM organization besides toward incessant HMM organization, projected coordination offerings an enhanced appreciation proportion aimed at thrice examination groups.

Fig. 9: Consequences of dissimilar structures scheduled in set 4-6

From the obtained data of our mixture NN based HMM coordination remains somewhat minor to individuals accomplished through the major arrangement which takes contended in place of connected Hindi writing appreciation opposition [20]. Also, the developed method is able to stand charity on behalf of presentations allocating through the exposed dictionary for the situation remains appeal constructed.

8. CONCLUSION :

Developed work projected trendy a mixture MLPNN/HMM scheme for Hindi written calligraphy appreciation wherever results productivity likelihood compression purposes for the disconnected HMM's situations stay approached through the MLP network. This resolution remained near revenue compensations for associated proper control of connectivity of neural although earning since the Monrovia categorization demonstrating. To circumvent a sophisticated deciphering complication primarily owing toward custom for together differences, the MLPNN remained impartial charity

proceeding with the exercise fragment for the proposed structure. Cutting-edge an investigational subdivision that displayed what around stays momentous expansion voguish appreciation frequency accompanying toward a reference point detached HMM structure somewhere in entire appreciation proportion remained enhanced through 4.25% by the projected mixture methodology. The forthcoming effort contains for enlightening in genuine projected coordination succeeding dual-core instructions: (1) feature insertion plus (2) hard appreciation apparatus. Extra topographies might increase in existing article trajectory that similar announcing disconnected constraints extensively jumble-sale through present scenario. Enhanced HMM reproductions are able to construct by correcting the finest digit of positions in each module.

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Modeling of Hybrid CNN Framework for Handwritten Character and Digit Recognition System

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Keywords:

OCR, Handwritten character recognition system (HCR), CNN, Network classification.

ABSTRACT

Purpose: In this paper highlights the recognition of hand-written Content/character problems that have been proposed. This study shows the emerging and widely used in many vision-based applications in recent years. In this work, the drawback of conventional handwriting recognition utilizes the statistical characteristics of individual Content/characters, and different subsets to recognize the different Content/characters are overcome.

Design/Methodology/Approach: To mitigate this problem several works have been motivated to incorporate a deep learning model for handwriting recognition and achieved significant performance improvement in recent times. In deep learning models, Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are providing promising solutions to automate the distinct feature extraction from all given training samples. In this work pre-processing measures have been used to explore the boundary details of input samples for CNN-based handwritten character and digit recognition systems. Here, we proposed a hybrid novel CNN model which combines the detailed feature extraction for final classification. The proposed CNN framework is trained using the Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology (MNIST) database.

Findings/Result: The performance validation includes both character and digits classification from given benchmark image sets. The validation also includes some self-built handwritten characters and digits for analyzing its resistance to the real-time capture. From the experimental results, it is observed that the variation inaccuracies are significant with the number of layers used in the CNN network. Finally, to validate the performance metrics of the proposed handwritten character recognition system it is compared with the existing state-of-the-art HCR models in terms of overall recognition accuracy.

Originality/Value: In this work, the drawback of conventional handwriting recognition utilizes the statistical characteristics of individual Content/characters, and different subsets to recognize the different Content/characters are overcome. The objectives for accommodating handwritten content/characters written in different formats are difficult to accomplish irrespective of the methodologies used for classification.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years automatic handwriting character recognition has been emerging steadily due to its wide range of enormous application potentials such as banking sectors, mobile phones, and computer-aided education [1]. As compared to other recognition systems HCR is dealing with several complications due to the enormous variety of handwriting styles of each individual. As compared to printed Content/characters recognizing handwritten Content/characters are comes with several challenges as follows: (1) Handwritten Content/characters comes with morphological and scale variations within the same classes; (2) Inter class similarity level of some of similar Content/characters are very high which makes poor detection rate. It is categorized into two types such as online and Offline HCR[2]. In both, cases for improved recognition accuracy different segmentation and feature extraction methods are used in many existing works. The recent advancements in character recognition technology emerging several parametric constraints that can extend its usage in a wide range of applications that required unique character identification[3][4]. In general character recognition are deployed with detailed analyzes of each unit to formulate the feature sets and extended with large sets of multi-modal data attributes to improve the accuracy[5]. Morphological measurements are the widely preferred technique to explore the dimension of any object of interest. Most of the existing HCR methods formulate templates with finite shape features and showed potential misclassification issues over features set level optimization [6].

In some cases, thinning of the input image is performed as pre-processing blocks just before the ROI segmentation [7]. During boundary evaluation, the lines that are separating each letter that is available in the document are explored as an extension to the pre-processing phase. This can be accomplished in many ways such as linear object projections or binary thresholding or clustering of the objects. This Character Segmentation segments each content/character forward to these objects into the feature extraction phase[8]. Finally, HCR allows some contextual information from each object to carry out auto-classification.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 gives the detailed analysis of the various related works on HCRmodels. Section 3 describes the proposed deep learning framework for a high-performance HCR system. Performance efficiency and guaranteed recognition rate of the proposed method are discussed with analysis and performance evaluation in section 4. Section 5 summarizes the work.

2. RELATED WORKS

Most existing works used HCR models for characterizing the digitized collections [4-5]. Moreover, HCR methods are highly sensitive to error accumulation over input. In particular, for handwritten documents, significant performance gaps are notable despite the advancement over time. But still, the importance of HCR systems is essential for processing any language even though its results are far from perfect. In some cases, complete probabilistic methods are used for HCRfor monolithic scan document systems and used as a prominent computational kernel in the NLP process. To narrow down the penalty gap using the most appropriate feature set models and use the most useful templates for network training is investigated in many recent works.

Much research has been devoted to natural language processing (NLP) to process over English languages rather than native languages. However, to perform data assessment over HCR performance and various stages of the recognition process different versions of the same input document is need to be produced which can incorporate all nonlinear changes. In [6] analyzed the impact of the nonlinear changes that may occur over

input over natural language processing (NLP) performance. Hereby performing various assessments such as ROI segmentation, letter recognition, data retrieval, feature set modeling, etc over existing OCR models and its impact in NLP is discussed. In [7] developed Tamil character recognition using novel OCR and NLP techniques. For performance validation, several inscription documents are collected from the Tamil Nadu government Archaeological Department and carried out pre-processing and ROI segmentation process. For ROI segmentation input RGB color images are transformed into grayscale and linearization is performed based on a threshold value. For template generation highly unified Scale Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) is used to explore the finite discrimination of each character. Content/characters are identified based on only the quantifiable textual features extracted leads to poor accuracy in the case of illuminated images. Extracted values with values outside these ROI ranges must be discarded from the classification. In [8] investigate various state-of-the-art NLP models with various levels and types of OCR noise to prove the sensitive level of classification performance. The performance degradation of each model is systematically analyzed using different languages. And also showed that many dictionary-based extrinsic OCR evaluations lead complexity and variability of the anatomic shapes will be varying depending on character types. In [9] fast Boolean matching and binary external symmetry axis constellation are jointly used to explore the finite details of each character pattern. Here orientations are encoded and combined to generate feature subset and hierarchical classification is introduced and recognized different Content/characters based on its discrimination in hamming distance over-extracted feature.

In [10] investigates the potential benefits of the MNIST dataset invalidating various CNN and deep learning approaches invented for handwritten character recognition systems. Significant challenges faced by different artificial intelligence techniques are discussed and relevant performance metrics are also analyzed in detail. In [11] developed multi-class Support Vector Machine model for an off-line HCR system which includes multi-modal feature extraction techniques. Here Feature set includes spatial information about individual Content/characters, mean, standard deviation, and gradient information. HCR system introduced in [12] using improved neural network technology mitigates the issues related to complex handwritten character recognition. For an improved classification rate, the input image is pre-processed and extracted structural features with associated optimization for multiple neural networks. The compatibility issues of existing CNN are discussed in [13] which provides the inherent statistical characteristics like computation cost, huge memory space, and requirement of larger sets of training samples. This property makes most of the conventional CNN not applicable for resource and energy-constrained IoT and mobile devices. To mitigate this problem Global Weighted Average Pooling model is introduced to optimize the parameters involved in a fully connected layer without compromising the quality metrics. Finally, the overall inference time of CNN is optimally reduced using the cascaded model. In [14] developed deep convolutional neural networks (DCNNs) and analyzed its performance metrics in Handwritten Bangla character recognition. DCNN offered discriminative features extraction and improved invariance over nonlinear distortions in the input during validation.

Deep learning model developed in [15] for character recognition with improved recognition rate using different types of directional feature maps in CNN network. This system also includes a novel data augmentation model formulated based on statistical characteristics of handwritten Chinese content/characters. For better recognition rate enlarged sets are used for training that incorporates global transformation associated with relevant local distortion. In [16] optimize the computation cost of CNN using some appropriate compression based on a unified algorithm with some insignificant accuracy loss. The CNN

network structure is simplified using channel pruning strategy and network parameters are optimized using quantization technique. In [17] proposed a novel multi-objective Jaya CNN feature learning model to learn all potential features from input images directly. Here an optimizer and multiplication layer is introduced with an activation layer. The network model learns the spatial patterns by analyzing the spatial correlations and the Multiplication layer is used to formulate the learning model. The weights used at each layer are normalized using an optimizer. Finally, it has experimented in the OCR system and performance metrics are validated using inter-class similarity and intra-class variance associated during recognition of Content/characters. In [18] developed optimal feature subset generation for recognizing the handwritten TamilContent/characters using the nearest interest point classifier model. Here most simplified matching vector-based approach is used for classification with an accuracy of 90.2% by incorporating a detailed feature analysis process after the feature extraction process.

In [17] portrays a novel methodology for signature verification and identification proof in an offline situation dependent on a quasi-multi resolution technique using GSC (Gradient, Structural, and Concavity) features for feature extraction. These highlights when utilized at the word level, rather than the character level, yield promising outcomes with correctness as high as 78% and 93% for check and ID, separately. This strategy was effectively utilized in our past theory of individuality of handwriting created at CEDAR-dependent on getting inside and between author statistical distance distributions. In [17], investigating mark check and ID as offline handwriting verification and identification process separately, we delineate a mapping from the handwriting domain to the signature domain.

Chaudhuri et al. (1998) have completely printed the Bangla OCR system[1]. Bazzi et al. (1999) have an Omni font open-vocabulary OCR system for English and Arabic [2]. Mahmud et al. (2003) have a complete OCR system for continuous Bengali characters [3]. Lehal et al. (2009) have a complete machine-printed Gurmukhi OCR system[4]. Kolak et al. (2003) have a generative probabilistic OCR model for NLP applications[5]. Van et al. (2020). Have assessing the impact of OCR quality on downstream NLP tasks[6]. Manigandan et al. (2017, August). Tamil character recognition from ancient epigraphical inscription using OCR [7]. Hamdi et al. (2020, August) have assessed and minimized the impact of OCR quality on named entity recognition [8]. Dash et al.(2016) developed BESAC explored Binary External Symmetry Axis Constellation for unconstrained handwritten character recognition[9]. Baldominos et al. (2019) have surveyed handwritten character recognition with most and emnist[10]. Katiyar et al. (2017) have an offline handwritten character recognition system using a support vector machine. American Journal of Neural Networks and Applications[11]. Li et al. (2017) have handwritten character recognition technology combined with artificial intelligence[12]. Li, Z et al. (2018) have built efficient CNN architecture for offline handwritten Chinese character recognition[13]. Alom et al. (2018) worked on handwritten Bangla character recognition using state-of-the-art deep convolutional neural networks. Computational intelligence and neuroscience [14]. Qu et al. (2018) worked on data augmentation and directional feature maps extraction for in-air handwritten Chinese character recognition based on the convolutional neural network[15]. Gan et al. (2020) have compressed the CNN architecture for in-air handwritten Chinese character recognition[16]. Das et al. (2020) have published MJCN: Multi-objective Jaya Convolutional Network for handwritten optical character recognition[17]. Deepa et al. (2020) have presented a novel nearest interest point classifier for offline Tamil handwritten character recognition [18]. Ghadekar et al. (2018) have worked on handwritten digit and letter recognition using hybrid DWT-DCT with known and SVM classifiers [19]. Cavalin et al. (2018) have Confusion matrix-based building of hierarchical classification [20].

3. OBJECTIVES

The above review shows that in recent years, the CNN framework is widely used in many vision-based applications. But the drawback of conventional handwriting recognition utilizes the statistical characteristics of individual content/characters and different subsets to recognize the different Content/characters. This paper proposes a scheme to overcome such drawbacks. Accordingly, the objectives of this research paper are:

- (1) To simulate a hybrid model of CNN-SVM for handwritten digit recognition that involves automatic feature generation using CNN and output prediction using SVM.
- (2) To extract the feature training and test the input set of MNIST for digital images.
- (3) To minimize the generalization error on unseen data in SVM, a hybrid model of CNN plus SVM is proposed.
- (4) An efficient modeling of hybrid CNN framework for handwritten character and digit recognition system is proposed.

4. CHARACTER RECOGNITION

4.1. Optical Character Recognition (OCR)

Optical Character Recognition (OCR) is a method of transforming handwritten/scanned images into state-encoded values. Here digital databases are created based on multi-model texture features from each segmented ROI text Content/character and used simple machine learning approaches to recognize each Content/character. In most cases, OCR offers an improved character recognition rate with some unified segmentation model and database generation.

4.2. Handwritten Character Recognition (HCR)

Hand-written character recognition (HCR) is used to recognize the individual Content/characters using appropriate feature set modeling and machine learning algorithms. It has been widely adopted for a wide range of languages across the world and to recognize each individual written character belonging to different languages uses various image processing techniques to model the classes. As compared to other recognition methods HCR is computationally complex due to the randomness of different individual handwritings which causes both intraclass variance and correlative inter-class similarity measures which makes the recognition a difficult task to accomplish with considerable accuracy. To overcome this problem highly abstract and invariant image features are needs to be used for classification.

Fig.1. Handwritten recognition system using CNN architecture

5. PROPOSED CNN MODEL

Here different Content/characters detected and isolated from given input samples network training is carried out using a CNN which is empowered to learn the distinct morphological patterns of all different classes with some finite discriminations. A convolutional neural network consists of several convolutional layers with appropriate activation functions and parameters as follows:

$$\square = \{w, B\}. \tag{1}$$

Where w is a set of convolution kernels, and B is a bias.

At each layer, the input I is convolved N numbers of kernels $w = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_N\}$ and associated biases $B = \{B_1, B_2, \dots, B_N\}$. During the convolution operation, a new feature map I_{mid} is generated at each layer.

An activation function is formulated from each of these feature maps to carry out non-linear transform over the input.

The process is involved in each layer is formulated by using Eqn. (2) as shown below:

$$I_{kCL} = g(w * I_{kCL-1} + B_{kCL-1}) \tag{2}$$

Where here, '*' the convolution operation and g denote the activation function. CL refers to the total number of convolution layers in the CNN network.

Fig.2. Sample MNIST dataset

In general pre-processing plays a significant role in CNN based handwritten recognition process. To formulate the input images into the most suitable form which can be easily used to learn the potential information is an essential task that needs to be accomplished before the network learning. Here gradient information's are extracted from input sample images with variance ranges from 0.2-0.5 as shown in Fig 4. the geometrical information available from gradient output is used for better normalization over labeled data and optimal discrimination among Content/characters and digits which are similar in appearance in handwritten format. Here sample images from MNIST dataset images were decomposed into a fixed image of size 28×28 . And hidden layers with 28

kernel/filter/patches are used with two different kernel sizes of 3×3 and 5×5 for extracting pixel and geometric features from input sample images. At each layer, all morphological and pixel information from input images is converted into neurons interconnections during the learning process. The concept of padding is also introduced in the proposed CNN architecture to get maximum accuracy. Here Padding is used to control the shrinking of the output of each convolutional layer.

Fig.3. ROI for isolating the Content/characters

6. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

6.1. Experimental Setups

To validate the performance metrics of the proposed deep learning framework in both handwritten digit and character recognition different learning parameters are used in the convolutional neural network which can produce optimal recognition accuracy and computational time. The network training parameter includes the learning rate of 0.01 and maximum epoch counts of 5. And CNN layers also include hyper-parameters which include kernel size (1–5), stride (1–3), dilation (1–2), and padding (1–2). Each of these parameters offers a different level of explorations about potential information like edges and corners from the input images in the hidden layers of the CNN, which also helps to normalize the data learned and needs to be processed at the subsequent layers for the final feature map generation. The first observation from Table 1 shows the importance of improved learning with the extended number of hidden layers. As compared to 3 layers CNN architecture inclusion of additional layers offers significant improvement in overall recognition accuracy. In particular, the discrimination level among inter-class similarity and consistency over intraclass variations was also optimally obtained in the 4-layer CNN model.

Fig.4.Direct sample image from MNIST

Fig.5. Pre-processed sample image from MNIST using gradient measure

The handwritten recognition system comprises of the following steps:

- Step 1. To collect benchmark handwritten digit and character images from the MNIST datasets.
- Step 2. By Class: In this work, 62 different classes are used which include digits [0-9], lowercase letters [a-z], and uppercase letters [A-Z].
- Step 3. To select 10 images from each class to formulate the training set.

- Step 4. To apply gradient measures as a pre-processing technique to explore the boundary details over the training dataset.
- Step 5. To formulate the CNN network model using three hidden layers and carried out a training process.
- Step 6. To use a learned model for the classification of digits and Content/characters.
- Step 7. To validate the performance metrics using classification accuracy.

Table 1: Performance comparison of proposed handwritten recognition using different hybrid CNN parameters

Model	Layer	Kernel size (k)	Stride (s)	Dilator (d)	Padding (p)	Recognition accuracy		
						Digit (0-9)	Lower case(a-z)	Upper case (A-Z)
Model1	Layer 3	3x3	2	2	2	94.67%	92.34%	93.29%
		5x5	3	1	1	92.89%	89.65%	92.87%
Mode2	Layer 4	3x3	2	2	2	95.54%	93.12%	94.1%
		5x5	3	1	1	93.56%	91.89%	93.6%

Fig.6. Performance comparison of proposed handwritten recognition using different hybrid CNN parameters

Table 2: Performance comparison of proposed geometric driven handwritten recognition using gradient information

Model	Layer	Kernel size (k)	Recognition accuracy		
			Digit (0-9)	Lower case(a-z)	Upper case (A-Z)
Direct learning from the input sample	Layer 4	3x3	95.54%	93.12%	94.1%
Gradient processed sample	Layer 4	3x3	97.34%	95.23%	97.1%

6.2. Data Acquisition

To evaluate the performance metrics of the proposed hybrid CNN model, experiments are conducted in the MNIST benchmark dataset which includes both letters and digits. The training sets are formulated with 25 images for each class. All training samples are processed using a gradient with variance level varied from 0.2-0.4 for finite boundary detailed exploration as shown in Figure. 7.

Figure7. Handwritten character recognition and annotation output

To evaluate the performance of the proposed HCR model for efficient character recognition the simulation experiment considers both samples from datasets and self-build handwritten Content/characters. Here for each evaluation, all individual's content/characters are randomly distributed all over the region and the experimental results evaluated both ROI selection using binary morphological operations and successive network classification separately.

6.3. State-Of-The-Art Comparison

To validate the performance metrics and associated recognition accuracy measurement of the proposed CNN framework comparative analyzes includes performance comparison with two prominent methods using the MNIST benchmark dataset. In Ghadekar et al. (2018) [19]) the authors used a multi-class support vector machine (SVM) for character recognition which includes two transform domain features were used namely

discrete cosine transform (DCT) and discrete wavelet transform (DWT). This ML approach showed recognition accuracy of 89.51% and 97.74% for letters and digits respectively. Here it is noted that transform domain features are not sufficient to incorporate useful discriminative characteristics of different letters as compared to digit classifications. Moreover, intraclass variations are very less for all digits which is most common for letters for both upper and lower cases along with inter-class similarities. Cavalin et al. (2018) [20]) introduced the CNN framework for improved learning from letters which showed superior classification accuracy of 93.63% which is outperform the existing ML approach for letter recognition. So many techniques were used in many existing learning methods for maximizing the recognition accuracy of MNIST. As compared to other competitive DL models proposed CNN method has superior recognition accuracy of 94.8% and 99.7% for letters and digits respectively. And the proposed model is also tested with self-build real-time handwritten images which give around 89.47% using 4-layer CNN.

Table 3: Performance comparison of proposed CNN model

Technique	Letters	Digits
DWT-DCT + SVM (Ghadekar et al. (2018)) [19]	89.51%	97.74%
CNN (Cavalin et al. (2018)) [20]	93.63%	99.46%
Proposed CNN model	94.8%	99.7%

Fig.8. Performance comparison of proposed CNN model

7. CONCLUSION

This paper attempted at creating an improved deep learning framework for handwritten recognition which includes both Content/characters and digits. By using an adaptive variance-based gradient formulation is used to explore the boundary details of each individual. The difference in the style of the handwritten

scripts is efficiently learned using CNN with multiple hidden layers. Self-build samples were also considered for experimental analyzes to validate the performance metrics of the developed DL-HCR methodology. An acceptable detection rate of more than 90% was attained across all different classes during performance validation. The efficiency of gradient driven CNN modeling handwritten character recognition showed improved system performance over benchmark HCR datasets

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